

Master's final project

Double Master in Industrial Engineering and Energy Engineering

Data analysis and evaluation of Multiport converter optimization in different scenarios

MEMORY

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Resum

El present Treball de Fi de Màster realitza una anàlisi exhaustiva sobre les diferents tecnologies utilitzades per a xarxes de distribució elèctrica mitjançant electrònica de potència, centrant-se en el potencial dels convertidors multiport (MPCs). Els MPCs presenten un gran potencial per facilitar la connexió de múltiples fonts d'energia i càrregues elèctriques, proporcionant una major flexibilitat per a la regulació dels fluxos de potència a la xarxa.

La metodologia proposada en aquest treball introdueix una optimització completa del conjunt de terminals connectats a un MPC, en contrast amb les metodologies tradicionals que dimensionen cada terminal de forma independent. Aquest enfocament permet reduir el sobredimensionament del sistema, amb una consegüent disminució dels costos d'instal·lació i operació. Per validar aquesta metodologia, s'han analitzat casos específics que simulen condicions reals d'operació, utilitzant el sistema IEEE de 33 busos.

Donat el alt cost computacional associat als paràmetres definits per a l'optimització dels fluxos de potència, s'han emprat tècniques avançades de machine learning, com autoencoders per a la reducció de dimensionalitat i k-means per a l'agrupament de dades. Aquestes eines no només permeten identificar patrons representatius, sinó que també redueixen la complexitat computacional en analitzar únicament els casos més significatius del sistema. L'eficàcia d'aquestes tècniques es valida mitjançant el baix error de reconstrucció obtingut amb els autoencoders i mètriques sòlides que avalen la qualitat dels clusters generats, assegurant que les dades utilitzades en l'optimització siguin representatives i precises.

En conclusió, aquest treball destaca no només el potencial dels MPCs com a solució clau en xarxes de distribució elèctrica, sinó també l'impacte de la metodologia presentada en optimitzar el seu dimensionament i reduir els temps de còmput. La integració de tècniques avançades de machine learning i enfocaments d'optimització conjunta reforça la utilitat dels Multiports Converters per assolir un sistema més eficient, flexible i econòmicament viable.

Resumen

El presente Trabajo de Fin de Máster realiza un análisis exhaustivo sobre las distintas tecnologías utilizadas para redes de distribución eléctrica mediante electrónica de potencia, centrándose en el potencial de los convertidores multipuerto (MPCs). Los MPCs presentan un gran potencial para facilitar la conexión de múltiples fuentes de energía y cargas eléctricas, proporcionando una mayor flexibilidad para la regulación de los flujos de potencia en la red.

La metodología propuesta en este trabajo introduce una optimización completa del conjunto de terminales conectados a un MPC, en contraste con las metodologías tradicionales que dimensionan cada terminal de forma independiente. Este enfoque permite reducir el sobredimensionamiento del sistema, con una consiguiente disminución en los costes de instalación y operación. Para validar esta metodología, se han analizado casos específicos que simulan condiciones reales de operación, utilizando el sistema IEEE de 33 buses.

Dado el alto coste computacional asociado a los parámetros definidos para la optimización de los flujos de potencia, se han empleado técnicas avanzadas de machine learning, como autoencoders para la reducción de dimensionalidad y k-means para el agrupamiento de datos. Estas herramientas no solo permiten identificar patrones representativos, sino que también reducen la complejidad computacional al analizar únicamente los casos más significativos del sistema. La eficacia de estas técnicas se valida mediante el bajo error de reconstrucción obtenido con los autoencoders y métricas sólidas que avalan la calidad de los clusters generados, asegurando que los datos utilizados en la optimización sean representativos y precisos.

En conclusión, este trabajo destaca no solo el potencial de los MPCs como solución clave en redes de distribución eléctrica, sino también el impacto de la metodología presentada en optimizar su dimensionamiento y reducir los tiempos de cómputo. La integración de técnicas avanzadas de machine learning y enfoques de optimización conjunta refuerza la utilidad de los MPCs para lograr un sistema más eficiente, flexible y económicamente viable.

Abstract

The present Master's Thesis conducts an exhaustive analysis of the different technologies used for electric distribution networks through power electronics, focusing on the potential of multiport converters (MPCs). MPCs present great potential to facilitate the connection of multiple energy sources and electrical loads, providing greater flexibility for regulating power flows in the network.

The methodology proposed in this work introduces a complete optimization of the set of terminals connected to an MPC, in contrast to traditional methodologies that size each terminal independently. This approach allows for a reduction in system oversizing, with a consequent decrease in installation and operation costs. To validate this methodology, specific cases simulating real operating conditions have been analyzed, using the IEEE 33-bus system.

Given the high computational cost associated with the parameters defined for the optimization of power flows, advanced machine learning techniques have been employed, such as autoencoders for dimensionality reduction and k-means for data clustering. These tools not only allow for the identification of representative patterns but also reduce computational complexity by analyzing only the most significant cases of the system. The effectiveness of these techniques is validated through the low reconstruction error obtained with the autoencoders and solid metrics that support the quality of the clusters generated, ensuring that the data used in the optimization are representative and accurate.

In conclusion, this work highlights not only the potential of MPCs as a key solution in electric distribution networks but also the impact of the proposed methodology in optimizing their sizing and reducing computation times. The integration of advanced machine learning techniques and joint optimization approaches reinforces the utility of MPCs to achieve a more efficient, flexible, and economically viable system.

Contents

Glossary	5
List of Figures	7
List of Tables	9
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Motivation	10
1.2 Scope and limitations of the project	11
1.3 Objectives	12
2 State of the Art	13
2.1 Growth of Renewable Energy Integration in Europe and Associated Challenges	13
2.2 Key Technologies for Flexible Power Distribution Systems	14
2.3 Multiport Converters (MPCs)	17
2.3.1 Approaches for MPC Sizing and Optimization	17
2.4 Machine Learning in Energy systems	21
2.4.1 Clustering in Energy Data Analysis	23
2.4.2 Dimensionality reduction in Energy Systems	26
3 Methodology	30
3.1 Data Clustering and Dimensionality reduction	31
3.1.1 Data extraction and Preprocessing	32
3.1.2 Approaches for clustering classification and dimensionality reduction	33
3.1.3 Transformation of the data and Splitting process	37
3.1.4 Implementation of the Autoencoder	38
3.1.5 Selecting the Best Autoencoder and Clustering Configuration	42
3.1.6 Selection of Representative Days	43
3.1.7 Creation of a New Scenario	44
3.1.8 Comparison between Original and New Scenario	45
3.2 Definition of the New Sizing Methodology MPCs	47
3.2.1 Renewables sizing	48
3.2.2 Proposed methodology MPC	49
3.2.3 Optimization problem	52
4 Results	53
4.1 Dimensionality reduction and clustering Results New Scenario	53
4.2 MPC Results and Comparative Analysis	59
5 Planification	67
6 Economic assessment	68
7 Enviromental assesment	68
8 Social and gender equality assessment	70
Conclusions	71
Future Work	72

9 Acknowledgments	73
Bibliography	74
Annex	81

Glossary

CIGRE International Council on Large Electric Systems. [17](#), [18](#), [70](#)

DBI Davies-Bouldin Index. [26](#)

DBSCAN density-based clustering non-parametric algorithm. [25](#)

HOP Hybrid Open Point. [14–16](#)

IEA International Energy Agency. [13](#), [14](#)

ML Machine Learning. [21–23](#)

MPC Multiports Converter. [10–21](#), [30](#), [31](#), [45](#), [47–54](#), [56–63](#), [66](#), [67](#), [70](#), [72](#)

NOP Normally Open Point. [7](#), [15](#), [16](#)

PCA Principal Component Analysis. [22](#), [26](#), [27](#)

PV Photovoltaic. [11](#), [14](#), [33–36](#), [44](#), [45](#), [48](#), [58](#)

SOP Soft Open Point. [14](#), [15](#), [20](#), [21](#)

VSC Voltage Source Converter. [16](#)

List of Figures

1	Evolution of renewable electricity generation [7]	13
2	Example of a Normally Open Point (Normally Open Point (NOP)) implementation [11]	15
3	Example of a Soft Open Point (SOP) implementation [14]	16
4	Example of a Hybrid Open Point (HOP) implementation [9]	16
5	Example of a MPC [15]	17
6	Terminal-Based MPC Configuration [1]	18
7	Ensemble-Based MPC Configuration [1]	19
8	Supervised Learning: Training and Prediction with Labeled Data [37]	23
9	Unsupervised Learning: Processing Unlabeled Data [37]	23
10	Clustering: Grouping Data into Distinct Clusters [45]	24
11	Clustering: Identifying Non-linear Data Structures [45]	24
12	Example of Architecture of Autoencoder [57]	28
13	Taxonomy of autoencoders, categorizing them by functional and structural distinctions [58]	29
14	Flowchart of the Methodology for Data Clustering and MPC Optimization	30
15	Flowchart of the MPC optimization process sizing methodology	31
16	Boxplot of Normalized Variables	33
17	Violin Plot of Normalized Variables	33
18	Silhouette Scores for Individual Variables (Consumption, Wind, PV)	34
19	Silhouette Scores for Bivariate Combinations (Consumption-WIND, Consumption-PV, PV-WIND)	35
20	Silhouette Score with the combination of all the variables (Consumption/PV/Wind)	36
21	Autoencoder Architecture	39
22	Flowchart of Baseline MSE Calculation	43
23	MAPE Values for the 18 Load Clusters	46
24	Comparison of Original and Selected Cluster (18) Load Profiles over the year	46
25	Frequency Distribution of iPLUG and Cluster 18 Load Profiles	47
26	Boxplot Comparison of iPLUG and Cluster 18 Load Profiles	47
27	Grid topology of 33 bus with MPC of four terminals case study	48
28	Reactive constraints of MPC [4]	51
29	Latent Space representation with the Autoencoder codification	54
30	Comparison of MSE between Autoencoder and Base model	55
31	Autoencoder Architecture: Compression and Reconstruction Process	56
32	Load and Generation profile of 33 bus case study Representative days	57
33	Comparison of Normalized Variable Distributions Across Clusters	58
34	Grid topology and results of the original methodology for MPC capacity	59
35	Grid topology and results of the modified methodology for MPC capacity	60
36	Comparison of MPC capacity across the different methodologies	60
37	Comparison of Renewable power generation across the different methodologies	61
38	Comparison Apparent power capacity by terminal across the different methodologies	62
39	Comparison of Reactive power by terminal across the different methodologies	64
40	Reactive power comparison by terminals and the grid	65
41	Project Workflow and Planning Overview	67
42	Pie chart distribution of CO_2 emissions	69
43	Key SDGs Supported by This Research	71

44	Example 1 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output	81
45	Example 2 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output	81
46	Example 3 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output	81
47	Example 4 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output	81
48	Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 0 and 1 over Time	82
49	Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 2 and 3 Over Time	82
50	Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 4 and 5 Over Time	82
51	Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 6 and 7 Over Time	82
52	Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 8 and 9 Over Time	83
53	Representative Daily Profiles for Cluster 10 and 11 over Time	83
54	Representative Daily Profiles for Cluster 12 over Time	83
55	Boxplot of PV Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis	84
56	Boxplot of WIND Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis	84
57	Boxplot of Consumption Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis	85
58	Voltage differences across the different methodologies	86
59	Line current differences across the different methodologies	86

List of Tables

1	Summary Statistics Before Normalization	33
2	Summary Statistics After Normalization	33
3	Mapping Dataset to Convolutional Autoencoder Input Format	37
4	Dataset Sizes After Splitting	38
5	Summary of Total Active Power and 50% in Renewables by Bus Group	48
6	Summary of Renewable Energy Sources	49
7	Converter costs derived from the original methodology. [4]	52
8	Best results of Cluster obtained	53
9	Comparison between the original and new methods	54
10	Results of Clusters, their Representative Days, and Weights	57
11	Comparison of Total Values with Percentage Difference	66
12	Comparison of Results: Modified vs Original Scenarios	67
13	Project Budget Breakdown	68
14	Total CO ₂ emissions resulting from the development of this thesis.	69

1 Introduction

In recent years, integrating renewable energy as part of the Transition towards net zero has highlighted the critical role of power converters. These devices act as a flexible interface between low-carbon technologies and the power grid [1], offering advanced levels of flexibility and controllability. Despite that, this transition [2] comes with significant challenges, such as the variability of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, the necessity for reliable energy storage systems, and the increasing adoption of other technologies such as heat pumps or electric vehicles by small consumers. These challenges require efficient and advanced technologies capable of optimizing the power flow in distribution networks.

Specifically, one of the alternative and efficient technologies suggested is **Multiports Converter (MPC)** which can act as a superior alternative to multiple individual converters in hybrid systems [3, 4]. The concept of **MPCs** facilitates the integration of renewable energy sources, storage systems, and loads through a single, streamlined device, reducing redundancy and enhancing overall system efficiency. Unlike traditional methods that optimize individual terminals separately [1], this unified optimization methodology evaluates power flow and capacity requirements across the entire **MPC** system. Treating the **MPC** as an interconnected ensemble enhances system flexibility, reduces redundancy, and ensures greater adaptability in distribution networks. The project explores various scenarios to demonstrate how this integrated strategy can maximize renewable energy integration, reduce curtailment, and enable more efficient energy distribution, particularly in hybrid systems with diverse energy profiles.

This project builds upon existing methodologies for **MPCs** by introducing a data-driven approach to optimize their operations as a unified system [1]. A significant challenge [4][5] in this process was the computational complexity associated with handling large datasets derived from wind and solar energy production and consumption patterns across diverse scenarios. To address this, unsupervised machine learning techniques were employed to analyze and group data, effectively identifying its most relevant features. Selecting representative data from clusters makes capturing the system's essential variability possible while minimizing redundancy, ensuring accurate scenario modeling, and reducing computational overhead [6].

In summary, the project is focused on the definition of a new methodology for the optimization of the sizing process of **MPCs**, involving techniques for dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques to datasets to improve decision-making and improve system efficiency

1.1 Motivation

The transition to sustainable energy systems introduces challenges due to the variability of renewable sources such as solar as well as wind and the complexity of new distribution networks as mentioned in section (1). Addressing these challenges requires the development of innovative solutions that optimize energy flows and the technological resources used in the grid.

MPCs efficiently integrate diverse energy sources, such as renewables and batteries, into a single device. However, traditional optimization methods focus on independent terminal optimization, limiting the full potential of the **MPCs**. A unified optimization approach is essential to enhance their adaptability and operational efficiency.

Moreover, the large amounts of data generated by renewable energy systems, such as hourly profiles of consumption as well as solar and wind generation, bring an additional challenge.

Managing this data efficiently is critical. Techniques with unsupervised learning address this challenge by reducing computational complexity while maintaining the main features and relevance of the data.

Despite the advancements in MPC technologies, further research is needed to validate their viability and define their performance in real operations conditions. Using data-driven methods is a critical point in demonstrating their full capabilities and ensuring their right integration in modern grids.

This project combines both lines of research with the aim of addressing the challenges of MPC optimization and efficient energy data management. Its development has the potential to contribute significantly to the flexibility and sustainability of modern energy systems, advancing the transition towards more efficient and resilient grids.

1.2 Scope and limitations of the project

The scope of this project is focused on the development and implementation of a new methodology in order to improve the optimization of the MPCs in distribution grids. Due to the challenges, such as the complexity of the data, computational efficiency, and the increase in renewable energy production, the project is proposing innovative solutions for these new energy systems. The scope and boundaries of the project are listed below:

- **Aim of the project**

- Definition of a methodology with unsupervised clustering classification methods, reducing the computation time for the analysis of the different scenarios.
- Transition of the optimization on terminal-based to the optimization on a unified system of the MPCs
- Creation of a new scenario with load profile, wind, and Photovoltaic (PV) generation
- Results comparison of the different methodologies applied (with the same case of study).

- **Data utilization**

- The project datasets include the annual profile of consumption, solar, and wind energy generation extracted from Deliverable D1.2 from the project iPLUG [4], which has been used to define the clustering methodology.
- Data extracted from various sources is used to validate the clustering methodology. Once validated, the methodology is applied to a new data scenario.

- **Boundaries of the project**

- The project's scope is limited to the optimization based on simulations; it does not include the physical implementation of the MPCs, and the results are based on specific scenarios created with the available data.
- The energy datasets and the data of the grid distribution are from a specific case of

study but could not cover all the potential configurations of the system.

- The optimization of the connection and location of the MPCs has not been considered.

- **Expected Results**

- Development of a methodology scalable to other datasets and future clustering in order to create new scenarios identifying the most representative data.
- Validation of the proposed optimization methodology for unified MPC systems, demonstrating improved operational efficiency and flexibility under realistic scenarios.
- Reduction in the sizing of MPCs while maintaining system performance, validated through comparison with the original methodology in equivalent scenarios.

1.3 Objectives

The project aims to implement a new methodology for designing and optimizing MPCs through innovative data-driven methodologies, incorporating data analysis and unsupervised clustering methodologies. The following objectives are defined according to the challenge, such as data complexity, computational efficiency, and system flexibility:

1. **Development of a methodology for analyzing energy data and consumption:** In order to identify patterns, trends, and correlations between the datasets relevant to the data-driven and MPC optimization
2. **Establishment of a reliable clustering framework for representative days selection:** Design and implement a reliable framework incorporating traditional and advanced machine learning techniques to group and select representative days.
3. **Validation of the cluster methodology:** Ensure that the selected days accurately capture the variability of the energy system according to the established metrics and compare results with the newly created scenario.
4. **Optimization of MPCs operation using representative days results:** With the selected representative days, focus on unified system optimization rather than terminal-based optimization
5. **Development and Transition of the new calculation methodology for flexibility of the MPCs:** Establish a scalable and flexible methodology for MPC operation, improving adaptability in hybrid energy systems.
6. **Evaluation of the proposed methodology performance:** Assess the scalability, efficiency, and effectiveness of the methodology across multiple scenarios, demonstrating its value in real scenarios.

2 State of the Art

This chapter presents the fundamental concepts and theories that support the analyses and methodologies developed in this work. It explores various power electronics solutions designed for modern distribution grids. Additionally, it covers the processes involved in calculating, sizing, and optimizing multi-port converters (MPCs) in electrical grids. Finally, it highlights the role of MPCs as an innovative solution for connecting multiple energy sources, such as electric vehicles, batteries, renewable energy generation, and electrical loads.

Recent research emphasizes the use of data-driven methods in the analysis and optimization of the grid and for the sizing of MPCs. These approaches process large amounts of data from energy consumption profiles, load variability, and network conditions to identify patterns and assist in decision-making. Techniques with machine learning models, such as clustering and dimensionality reduction, are applied to reduce the complexity of the datasets, identify the key features and patterns, and utilize the most relevant information to evaluate scenarios and obtain optimized results according to the representative data.

By examining these trends and innovations, this chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the methodologies currently being investigated to improve the flexibility and dimensioning of MPCs. This theoretical framework establishes a solid foundation for understanding the new approaches proposed in this thesis, especially in the context of data-driven analysis and optimization in power grids with the integration of MPCs.

2.1 Growth of Renewable Energy Integration in Europe and Associated Challenges

The integration of renewable energy sources in Europe has been growing over the past two decades due to the commitment to reducing carbon emissions, advancing toward a more sustainable energy system and supportive policies [7].

Figure 1: Evolution of renewable electricity generation [7]

According to the [International Energy Agency \(IEA\)](#), renewable energy generation in Europe

has grown substantially, with [PV](#), wind, and biomass playing key roles in the transition, as it is possible to see in [Figure 1](#).

In 2021, renewable energy sources were around 20% Europe's total final energy consumption, following a tendency from 2000 until 2021 of 115%. Among the different renewable sources, wind energy was the second largest contributor with 39 % of total generation from renewables, followed by Solar [PV](#) 17.5% [[7](#)].

According to the [IEA](#)'s projections, this trend is likely to continue growing, so the integration of these sources into the grid presents different challenges. According to [[8](#)], some of the primary challenges are:

- **Intermittency and Variability:** The dependence on weather conditions leads to fluctuations in energy production, which increases the difficulty of planning and managing power flow for grid operators.
- **Grid Stability and Frequency Regulation:** The variability of renewable energy sources affects grid stability, requiring systems like energy storage to mitigate these issues.
- **Energy Storage Needs:** Due to the fluctuations in renewable energy generation, there are periods of excess energy production that cannot be consumed and need to be stored for later use when renewable generation is low.
- **Grid Infrastructure:** The current grid infrastructure was designed for centralized power generation and is not well-equipped to handle the decentralized and fluctuating nature of renewable energy. Significant upgrades are needed to enable efficient power transport from renewable sources, and grid modernization is essential to integrate new technologies. This modernization is critical to improving grid flexibility and ensuring it can handle real-time energy supply and demand variations.
- **Regulatory Policies and Market Adaptation:** The growing share of renewable energy in the grid requires the adaptation of regulatory frameworks and market mechanisms. Policies need to promote renewable energy while ensuring that grid operators can maintain grid stability. Thus, effective regulatory policies must be implemented to support the integration of renewables into the grid.

2.2 Key Technologies for Flexible Power Distribution Systems

The growth of renewable energy sources detailed in [section 2.1](#) in Europe and the challenges associated with their integration into the grid has increased the need for solutions to enhance the flexibility and reliability of power distribution networks [[1](#)]. Some innovative approaches that enable advanced power control, network configuration, and optimization of distributed energy sources have already been developed. That innovation ensures the reliability of modern electrical grids [[1, 2](#)]

Advancements in power electronics and hybrid systems are replacing the traditional network components with devices that allow dynamic management of different energy sources interconnected between them. These technologies, such as [Soft Open Point \(SOP\)](#)'s, [Hybrid Open Point \(HOP\)](#)'s, and ([MPCs](#)), aim to reduce energy losses, manage renewable energy integration, and effectively control the power flow [[1, 2, 9](#)]

By incorporating this technology, research confirms the role of new control strategies, system improvement, and flexibility integration in distribution networks. Their implementation supports more adaptative and reliable operations, enabling the grid to respond effectively to current and future demands.

In order to provide a comprehensive understanding of these solutions, this section starts with the traditional concept of the distribution networks **NOPs**, progressing to more advanced technologies such as **SOPs**, **HOPs**, and **MPCs**, highlighting their importance in modern power systems.

Normally Open Points (NOP))

The **NOPs** are tie switches [11] situated in predefined locations in the electrical networks, and they are kept open under normal operating conditions. They segment the network, ensuring flexibility for fault isolation, maintenance, or reconfiguration of the network [12].

With the circuits opened through the **NOPs**, the load is redistributed, and it is isolated in the problematic sections without interrupting the supply of the entire network.

Figure 2: Example of a Normally Open Point (**NOP**) implementation [11]

NOPs are simple and cost-effective solutions widely used in traditional distribution systems. However, due to their static nature and the manual processes required for reconfiguration (Figure 2, their adaptability and effectiveness are limited for the requirements of modern grids, particularly those with high penetration of renewable energy sources due to the high fluctuation in the generation, according to that, the limitations of **NOPs** have become increasingly apparent [13].

Soft Open points (SOPs))

The **SOPs** are power electronic devices that were designed to replace the **NOPs** in distribution networks [13, 12]. The devices enable reactive power compensation, voltage regulation and power flow control, providing more flexibility and efficiency compared to the limited and static capabilities of **NOPs**.

Figure 3: Example of a Soft Open Point (SOP) implementation [14]

The design is typically based on two back-to-back Voltage Source Converter (VSC) (3), which enable bidirectional power flow and dynamic control, balancing the power and regulating the voltage. The study demonstrates that these capabilities result in better integration of renewable energy sources and a reduction in network losses, which are critical for modern distribution systems[12].

Hybrid Open Points (HOPs)

As described in paper [9], the HOPs are devices that consist of an electromechanical switch connected in parallel with a power converter (Figure 4). These devices are designed to provide higher capacity to the network in interconnected distributed power grids. The switch enables efficient bulk power transfer, while the power converter provides precise control and targeted power flow when the switch is open.

Figure 4: Example of a Hybrid Open Point (HOP) implementation [9]

These devices can be configured to replace NOPs, adapting to different operational needs. Their versatility allows them to operate effectively in scenarios where fault levels or radiality constraints are critical, ensuring reliable performance in a wide range of applications. Moreover, HOPs are recognized for their cost-effectiveness because they reduce the size and cost of the power converter compared to traditional solutions, all while maintaining full functionality [9].

Multiport Converters (MPCs)

The MPC's are technology that can facilitate the large-scale integration of distributed renewable energy sources, allowing the interconnection of multiple electrical grids and devices. These converters are designed to operate with AC or DC systems and can perform at different voltage levels, frequencies, phase configurations, and grounding schemes [10].

Figure 5: Example of a MPC [15]

As illustrated in Figure 5, MPC is an alternative allowing multiple connections with different types of energy sources.

2.3 Multiport Converters (MPCs)

According to the objectives of this project, which are focused on the definition of a new methodology in order to optimize the sizing process of the MPCs, this section explores the previous contributions of the current methodologies established and their results. Following this, the new research directions and approaches proposed in this project are introduced, aiming to address the limitations of existing methods and improve the efficiency and adaptability of the sizing optimization process of MPCs.

2.3.1 Approaches for MPC Sizing and Optimization

The different methodologies for calculating and optimizing MPCs are primarily focused on the optimal sizing and design process, which includes considerations for the topology of the grid [1, 2, 3, 4], the analysis of the MPCs flexibility, losses and cost minimization. The methodologies are developed under representative scenarios, enabling efficient optimization while accounting for variations in renewable energy production and availability, energy demand, and operational constraints.

Terminal-based Approach in D1.2 [10]

Specifically, the work presented in Deliverable D1.2 introduces a detailed framework for the optimization of Multipor Converters (MPCs) based on terminal optimization. This methodology was applied to the International Council on Large Electric Systems (CIGRE) European MV distribution network, which serves as the benchmark case study.

The CIGRE Task Force C6.04.02 network comprehensively represents European medium-voltage distribution systems, including topology, transformer specifications, line parameters, and feeder configurations. According to the established Benchmark model, the D1.2 methodology ensures the validity of the optimization results, making them applicable to real-world scenarios. This case study provides the basis for evaluating power flow, constraint limits in operation, and the economic implications of MPC implementations, establishing a reference point for comparing with other methodologies of calculation.

This methodology optimizes the power flow, capacity, and cost of each terminal connected to the MPC separately (Figure 6). This approach allows for an accurate evaluation of terminal-specific

contributions to the overall system.

Figure 6: Terminal-Based MPC Configuration [1]

The key features of the approach in D1.2 focuses on:

- **Terminal-based sizing optimization:** The terminals of the MPC are designed and sized according to the maximum capacity independently, with the previous definition of the connections to specific feeders or buses, ensuring that the power converter design aligns with the energy needs.
- **Individual power flow analysis:** Active and reactive power constraints are defined per terminal, enabling a detailed understanding of how each terminal contributes to the network's overall operational efficiency and flexibility.
- **Localized Cost evaluation:** with the evaluation of costs at the terminal level, the methodology ensures a detailed optimization of investment and operational expenditures, useful in complex distribution network topologies.

It employs representative day selection to reduce the computational complexity according to different indicators of the datasets, grouping the data, creating a subset of representative days, and ensuring computational feasibility while preserving the accuracy of the analysis. Reducing the number of days to analyze allows for precise sizing and placement of multiport converters (MPCs) while considering the interconnections with other grid elements, such as renewable energy sources and batteries.

The terminal-based approach serves as a baseline for optimizing MPCs and analyzing the impact on distribution systems. Considering this simplification, the analysis provides consistent insights into system flexibility, operational constraints, and cost optimization under realistic data.

Based on this methodology, the results demonstrate the technical, operational, and economic feasibility of Multiport Converters (MPCs) in distribution systems. Case studies on the CIGRE medium-voltage network and the IEEE 33-bus system showed the following results:

- **Impact of Generation Capacity:** The highest variability in MPC sizing is observed with

changes in installed generation capacity. In scenarios 1 and 2, where terminal power can drop to zero, MPCs become impractical for curtailment reduction.

- **Cost Optimization:** Adding 1 MVA of MPC capacity was economically justified if it results in an annual generation increase of at least 300 MWh, highlighting the importance of balancing investment with energy output.
- **Loss Reduction:** MPCs demonstrated the potential of reducing system losses and optimizing active and reactive power flows, specifically in distribution grids with high levels of renewable integration.
- **Payback Periods:** The economic analysis confirmed that MPCs installations are viable in scenarios with high renewable penetration and become more effective when providing additional grid services.
- **Voltage Regulation and Flexibility:** MPCs improved voltage profiles across the network, maintaining values within acceptable limits under varying load and generation conditions with a range of $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value.

Ensemble-Based MPC sizing Optimization

As detailed in section 2.3, the optimization of MPCs is a crucial point for the efficient management and integration of renewable sources along the distribution grids. The approach detailed in section 2.3.1 is focused on a traditional approach based on the optimization of every terminal of the MPCs independently, where each port of the MPC is sized, designed, and controlled independently. However, recent tendencies and advancements are promoting ensemble-based optimization strategies, treating the MPC as a whole [1].

The methodology for sizing optimization of Multiport Converters (MPCs) capacity is based on treating all terminals as an integrated system rather than optimizing them independently. This approach ensures a balanced allocation of converter capacities and improves overall system performance and flexibility.

Figure 7: Ensemble-Based MPC Configuration [1]

Figure 7 shows a configuration of MPCs based on a centralized multiplexer that coordinates multiple power sources (P[1], P[2], P[3]). The multiplexer optimizes active and reactive power

flow between the terminals, enabling the coordinated operation to minimize losses and improve system stability. This approach is ideal for integrating renewables and storage in flexible grids [1].

The key features of the approach in Multiplexing Power Converters focus on [1]:

- **Reconfigurable Converter Design:**

- Traditional Soft Open Points (SOPs) use fixed-capacity converters connected directly to feeders, limiting flexibility and increasing costs.
- The Multiplexed Soft Open Point (MOP) design employs multiplexers to dynamically connect converters to multiple feeders, enhancing active and reactive power management.
- Compared to traditional SOPs, the MOP design reduces required converter capacity by up to 24%, achieving significant cost savings while maintaining flexibility in power management.

- **Integrated Sizing and Optimization:**

- Conventional designs size each terminal independently, often oversizing the dimension of the MPC.
- The MPC methodology optimizes all terminal capacities simultaneously using strategies such as uniform allocation, bisection, and specific ratios to balance loss reduction and flexibility.
- This integrated sizing achieves 92% of the performance of an idealized system with only three converters, demonstrating its effectiveness with fewer components.

- **Flexibility Assessment:**

- Evaluates system flexibility using feasible power transfer sets to quantify operational limits.
- The methodology increases the capability chart volume (CCV) by over 100%, enabling greater operational flexibility compared to fixed SOPs.

- **Principal Advantages:**

- **Performance Enhancement:** Converters operate closer to their maximum capacity, maximizing efficiency.
- **Cost Reduction:** Dynamic reconfiguration eliminates the need for oversizing converters, reducing investment costs while maintaining the performance.
- **Scalability:** The design supports future expansion, accommodating additional feeders or converters for growing network demands and integrating high shares of renewable energy.

This methodology addresses the limitations of traditional **SOP** designs and the optimization of **MPCs** by terminal by treating the system as an integrated unit. It provides flexible, efficient, and cost-effective solutions for modern distribution networks, achieving higher performance with fewer components and lower costs [1].

2.4 Machine Learning in Energy systems

Machine Learning (ML) is a branch of Artificial Intelligence (IA), and, taking into account the growing complexity and evolving challenges of the energy sector over the past years, it has become a transformative and useful tool for the sector, commonly used for a wide range of applications. [16]

According to the availability of extensive datasets containing valuable information related to energy consumption, generation, and seasonal patterns, **ML** provides the ability to analyze large amounts of data efficiently. It is able to uncover complex relationships, reduce data dimensionality, and make accurate predictions, which have revolutionized energy management and optimization [17].

ML is used not only for forecasting and system optimization but also to understand complex patterns within different datasets, such as those related to temporal and consumption variability [17]. For instance, clustering methods and dimensionality reduction techniques are widely used to classify groups of data with the same features among the same datasets and compress high-dimensional data into lower-dimensional representations while retaining essential information. These techniques are particularly valuable for finding representative days in energy systems, identifying seasonal trends, and enabling more targeted analysis. [18]

Considering the different applications [19, 20], it explains the key applications of **ML** in energy systems, highlighting its relevance and effectiveness in addressing current challenges:

Energy Demand Forecasting

Energy demand forecasting is an essential aspect in the operation and management of energy systems, allowing grid operators to anticipate the future state and performance of the grid to make decisions based on the data. Accurate forecasting models are critical in order to maintain grid stability, optimize resource allocation, and support the integration of renewable energy sources. **ML** has significantly been integrated as a transformative tool, enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of energy demand forecasts using complex datasets and advanced computational algorithms.

Recent advancements in **ML** techniques have introduced complex models for long-term and short-term energy demand forecasting due to their better performance than traditional statistical models. For instance, Deep Learning models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, have been used to extract nonlinear relationships and temporal dependencies in energy consumption data. These methods improve the prediction with different variations along the data, making them effective in dynamic and integrated energy systems. [21, 22]

Additionally, there are probabilistic approaches, such as Masked Multi-Step Probabilistic Forecasting, which consider uncertainties in electricity demand, enhancing the forecast reliability due to considering possible new scenarios based on historical data. These methods combine

historical consumption patterns with external variables such as weather conditions, providing robust prediction between short- and mid-term planning for the grid operators. [23]

Moreover, dimensionality reduction techniques such as [Principal Component Analysis \(PCA\)](#) and Autoencoders play a key role in improving the scalability of ML models. These tools preprocess high-dimensional datasets, extracting essential features while retaining key patterns. [24, 25] ML-based energy demand forecasting shows how advanced computational methods address critical challenges in modern energy systems, improving not only the operational efficiency but also the preparation of the operation of the grid based on historical data.

Optimization of Energy Generation and Distribution

Optimization of energy generation and distribution is another of the key applications of ML in energy systems. As mentioned in section 2.1, the integration of renewable energy sources, growing demand variability, and the optimization in real time of resource allocations presents the ML as a technique able to face these challenges, transforming the traditional optimization methods into real-time adjustments improving the time of response and efficiency [26, 27].

One of the most powerful ML techniques in this field is Reinforcement learning (RL). RL algorithms can learn optimal strategies in front of dynamic energy pricing, real-time grid balancing and demand-side management. This technique is applied in smart grids, optimizing energy pricing and balancing the generation and consumption of the system [28, 29].

Other techniques applied involve predictive models, such as Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs), which analyze factors such as historical consumption, energy prices, and weather conditions in order to recommend optimal generation and distribution strategies. The models mentioned are commonly used in microgrid management, supporting the energy sharing between renewables and conventional energy sources.[30]

Dimensionality Reduction and Complex Pattern Analysis

Energy datasets commonly contain high-dimensional and heterogeneous variables, such as weather conditions and different generation profiles depending on source and hourly consumption. This complexity creates a challenge for clustering, simulation, and forecasting tasks. Dimensionality reduction techniques have become fundamental tools for facing these datasets, simplifying their structure without losing essential information. [33] [34]

Methods more traditional like PCA have been used in energy systems to reduce dimensionality while retaining significant features. PCA, for instance, has been applied to identify dominant energy consumption patterns and preprocess data for load forecasting models [35]. However, PCA's limitations in capturing nonlinear relationships have led to the adoption of advanced techniques.

Recent developments have focused on *Autoencoders* [36], a type of neural network designed for nonlinear dimensionality reduction. Autoencoders compress high-dimensional data into compact latent representations. The main application of this field are:

1. **Energy Load Profiling:** Compressing hourly consumption data into manageable representations for clustering.

2. **Anomaly Detection:** Extracting key patterns to identify outliers in energy generation or consumption.
3. **Grid Optimization:** Reducing computational complexity in simulations of energy distribution networks.

These techniques simplify the handling of high-dimensional data and enable more accurate and efficient analysis in energy systems.

2.4.1 Clustering in Energy Data Analysis

As mentioned before, **ML** can be classified into two main categories: supervised and unsupervised learning. [37]

Supervised learning uses labeled data in order to create an algorithm that predicts correct outputs, as shown in Figure 8. In energy systems, supervised learning is commonly applied in tasks such as:

- **Demand forecasting:** Models learn from historical consumption patterns to predict future energy demand, enabling more efficient energy management and planing. [38]
- **Anomaly detection:** Labeled datasets help identify irregular system behavior, such as outages or overloads. [39, 40]

In contrast, **Unsupervised learning**, as shown in the Figure 9, identifies hidden patterns and relationships but with unlabeled data. This approach is particularly used in clustering energy profiles, where the objective is to group similar days or generation/consumption patterns without predefined labels. By uncovering intrinsic structures within the data, unsupervised learning facilitates:

- Creation of representative datasets for reduce the time computation
- Identifying seasonal trends in renewable energy generation [41]

Figure 8: Supervised Learning: Training and Prediction with Labeled Data [37]

Figure 9: Unsupervised Learning: Processing Unlabeled Data [37]

After the nature of the problems normally with unlabeled datasets, being unsupervised learning, clustering has emerged as a key tool for analyzing energy datasets. The following section goes into clustering methodologies and their role in modern energy systems.

Clustering methods

Clustering, a subset of unsupervised learning, focuses on grouping unlabeled data into clusters based on similarity. Unlike supervised learning, clustering does not rely on predefined labels but instead identifies natural groupings within the data. This makes clustering particularly effective for addressing problems where the underlying structure of the data is unknown or difficult to define manually [42].

In the context of energy systems, clustering serves as a powerful tool for simplifying high-dimensional datasets, such as hourly consumption profiles or renewable generation data. By grouping similar patterns, clustering enables:

- **Reduced computational complexity:** Clustering methods can identify representative subsets of data, significantly reducing the resources required for simulations and optimization tasks. For instance, clustering has been used to group representative days in energy simulations, minimizing computational time without sacrificing accuracy [43].
- **Enhanced understanding of energy behavior:** By identifying clusters, analysts can uncover insights into seasonal trends, peak load periods, and variability in renewable generation. This information is critical for planning and integrating renewable energy into the grid efficiently [44].

Additionally, as shown in Figure 10 and 11, clustering results are often influenced by the choice of method and the assumptions about the geometry of the data. The number and shape of clusters are undefined, and different algorithms may produce different results, underscoring the need to select clustering techniques carefully based on the dataset's characteristics. [45]

Figure 10: Clustering: Grouping Data into Distinct Clusters [45]

Figure 11: Clustering: Identifying Non-linear Data Structures [45]

Principal Clustering methods

Several clustering methods are commonly used in energy data analysis depending on the nature of the datasets [46]:

- **Hierarchical Clustering:** Hierarchical clustering is a method of clustering based on building a dendrogram representing the hierarchical relationships between data points, allowing flexibility in selecting the desired level of granularity. The number of clusters is unknown, and it is effective for small datasets, it can struggle with scalability and performance when applied to larger datasets [47].
- **Density-based clustering non-parametric algorithm (DBSCAN):** is a method that groups

data points based on regions of high density and identifies outliers as noise. It is used for datasets with irregular-shaped clusters and does not require a predefined number of clusters. Its performance is highly dependent on the choice of hyperparameters. Additionally, [density-based clustering non-parametric algorithm \(DBSCAN\)](#) can face challenges when applied to high-dimensional datasets due to the difficulty in defining density in such spaces. [48, 49]

- **K-means:** is one of the most used clustering methods due to its simplicity and computational efficiency. The data is divided into K clusters minimizing the variance within clusters, making it ideal for large energy datasets. However, the number of clusters has to be defined in advance, which implies the use of other techniques to evaluate the best number of clusters. [50]

Metrics for Assessing the Quality of Clusters

Assessing the quality of clusters is critical to ensure that the clusters generated reflect meaningful patterns in the data [51]. The main metrics used are described below:

1. Silhouette Coefficient

The silhouette coefficient simultaneously measures the cohesion within a cluster and the separation between clusters. It is calculated for each point and its value ranges from -1 to 1:

- **1:** Indicates that points are perfectly grouped within their cluster and well separated from other clusters.
- **Between 0.5 and 1:** Suggests well-defined clusters, implying a good structure of the groups.
- **Between 0 and 0.5:** Reflects a weak cluster structure, where points are close to the boundary between clusters or not clearly differentiated.
- **0:** Indicates that the points are equidistant between two neighboring clusters.
- **Negative values (below 0):** Suggests that the points are misallocated, as they are closer to the neighboring cluster than to their own.

The formula is:

$$\text{Silhouette} = \frac{b - a}{\max(a, b)}$$

where:

- a is the average distance between the point and the other points in the same cluster.
- b is the average distance between the point and the nearest cluster to which it does not belong.

In general, an average silhouette coefficient greater than 0.5 indicates well-defined clusters, while values between 0.2 and 0.5 may reflect a weak structure, and values below 0 suggest incorrect or inefficient clustering [51, 53].

2. Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI)

The Davies-Bouldin index evaluates the relationship between the compactness of the clusters

(how compact they are) and their separation (distance between clusters). It is calculated as:

$$DBI = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \max_{j \neq i} \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{d_{i,j}}$$

where:

- K is the number of clusters.
- σ_i is the average within-cluster dispersion for cluster i .
- $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between the centroids of the clusters i and j .

A lower **Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI)** indicates better cluster quality, as it reflects compact and well-separated clusters. This metric is useful in energy data with clusters of similar sizes [51].

3. Elbow Method

The Elbow Method is a visual technique to determine the optimal number of clusters (K). It plots the sum of squared distances within clusters (WCSS) against different values of K . The formula of the WCSS is:

$$WCSS = \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{x \in C_i} \|x - \mu_i\|^2$$

where:

- C_i is the cluster i .
- μ_i is the cluster centroid i .

The "elbow" of the graph represents the point where adding more clusters no longer significantly improves clustering [52].

4. Gap Statistic

The Gap statistic compares the obtained clusters' quality with the randomly generated dataset's expected quality. A higher Gap value indicates better cluster formation. The formula is:

$$\text{Gap}(k) = \mathbb{E}[\log(WCSS_{\text{random}})] - \log(WCSS_k) \quad (1)$$

This metric is robust to noise and useful in data with less obvious patterns. [51]

2.4.2 Dimensionality reduction in Energy Systems

Energy systems generate huge volumes of high-dimensional data, such as hourly consumption profiles, renewable generation and weather conditions. Dimensionality reduction allows these data to be simplified without losing key information, making them more manageable for tasks such as clustering, simulation and forecasting.

There are two main approaches to dimensionality reduction in this field:

1. Linear techniques, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA).
2. Non-linear methods, represented by autoencoders, an advanced neural network.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Dimensionality reduction techniques are critical for simplifying high-dimensional energy datasets. Among them, [PCA](#) stands out for its statistical rigor and widespread application in the field. [PCA](#) is a statistical method that transforms the original data into a set of principal components, where each component is a linear combination of the original variables. This method:

- Reduces redundancies by identifying directions of maximum variance in the data.
- Retains key information, prioritizing principal components with higher variance.

[PCA](#) has been applied in various energy-related studies, including:

1. **Identification of dominant consumption patterns:** [PCA](#) is used to analyze historical consumption data and reduce it to a few key components, making it easier to understand the main factors affecting energy demand. For instance, it has been applied to detect patterns in residential and industrial energy consumption, aiding utilities in optimizing resource allocation [55].
2. **Energy load forecasting:** In forecasting studies, [PCA](#) is applied to reduce noise in meteorological and renewable generation data before feeding prediction models. This approach enhances the accuracy of predictive models by focusing on the most relevant variables, such as wind speed and solar radiation [56].

In this study, [PCA](#) serves as a foundational technique to analyze and preprocess energy datasets, complementing advanced models like autoencoders.

Autoencoders

Autoencoders are a type of neural network designed to learn compressed representations of input data. Unlike traditional techniques, autoencoders can capture non-linear relationships in the data, making them particularly suitable for domains where dependencies between variables are complex [57]. Autoencoders consist of three main components:

- **Encoder:** reduces the dimensionality of the data, extracting a compressed representation.
- **Latent Space:** Intermediate representation that encapsulates the main features of the data.
- **Decoder:** Reconstructs the original data from the latent representation, minimizing the loss of information.

Figure 12: Example of Architecture of Autoencoder [57]

According to the Medium article [57] as mentioned before, the most important function is the ability to learn a compressed representation of the input data used to reconstruct the original, being a key tool for dimensionality reduction (capturing complex relationships), feature learning by the extraction of relevant patterns from input data and data denoising for data visualization.

Hyperparameters of the Autoencoder [58]

Autoencoders, as a neural network model, require the definition of hyperparameters before the training process. These hyperparameters directly influence the model's performance, and their choice can determine how accurately the autoencoder can learn and generalize from the data. Some hyperparameters are generally fixed before training, while others can be dynamically adjusted during the training process. The common hyperparameters of the different types of Autoencoders are:

- **Number of Hidden layers:** The number of hidden layers in an autoencoder defines the network's ability to learn and capture complex patterns in the data. While a higher number of layers can improve the model's ability to represent these patterns, it also increases the risk of overfitting, especially if the model becomes too complex for the available data. This hyperparameter is useful when the model needs to capture more complex relationships in the data, but should be carefully adjusted as if the model starts to overfit, it may be necessary to reduce the number of layers or employ regularisation techniques.
- **Number of Neurons in each layer:** The number of neurons in each layer determines the network's ability to represent and learn patterns in the data. As we increase the number of neurons, the network has more capacity to learn complex patterns, but it also increases the risk of overfitting, which can complicate the optimization process and increase training time. This parameter is adjusted according to the size and complexity of the dataset and must be carefully calibrated to prevent the model from becoming unnecessarily complex.
- **Size of latent Space:** The size of the latent space is key to defining how much data is compressed during the training process. A small latent space size forces the model to learn more compact representations, which improves generalisation, but if it is too small, it can result in a significant loss of information. On the other hand, a large latent space allows more features of the data to be represented, but may decrease the generalisability

of the model. This hyperparameter is adjusted to find a balance between the model's capability and the complexity of the data.

- **Activation function:** Trigger functions are essential for introducing nonlinearities into the model, allowing it to learn complex patterns between variables. The choice of activation function affects how the network learns, and common choices include sigmoid, tanh, ReLU, and SELU. ReLU is especially efficient in deep networks, while sigmoid or tanh are useful when you need to limit the output to a specific range. The activation function should be chosen based on the data and the specific task, as it directly influences the learning capability of the autoencoder.

Objective function [58]

In order to minimize the difference between the input data and the reconstructed data, Autoencoders use specific objective functions to guide the learning process. These functions measure the quality of the data reconstruction and are selected according to the type of data and the objective of the model. For example, Mean Squared Error (MSE) is ideal for continuous data such as images, while Cross Entropy Loss (CEL) is used for binary data. Advanced models such as Variational Autoencoders (VAE) incorporate probabilistic terms into their objective function to allow for the generation of new data.

Classification of Autoencoders

The Figure 13 presented summarises the main types of autoencoders, classified according to their architecture and functionality, such as generative, recurrent and graph-based autoencoders. Each variant is adapted to specific applications, depending on the characteristics of the data and the objectives of the model. [58].

Figure 13: Taxonomy of autoencoders, categorizing them by functional and structural distinctions [58]

In the article 'A Survey of Autoencoders' (2023) [58], convolutional autoencoders (CAE) are highlighted as a key architecture for processing spatial data, such as images. Unlike traditional autoencoders that employ dense layers, CAEs use convolutional layers in both the encoding and decoding process. This allows them to capture local features, such as edges and textures, and to build hierarchical representations that integrate simple and complex patterns.

Their main applications include noise reduction, image reconstruction, and segmentation, where they excel in preserving spatial structure and generating accurate results. Compared to traditional autoencoders, CAEs are more efficient at processing data with complex spatial structures and adaptable to various contexts.

In summary, convolutional autoencoders are an indispensable tool in modern machine learning,

especially in tasks involving spatial data. Their ability to maintain the intrinsic structure of data and extract meaningful representations positions them as a key technology in computer vision and spatial data analysis.

3 Methodology

The methodology defined in this project is divided into two main parts. The first part is based on the dimensionality reduction of the datasets and data clustering in order to determine representative days for the case of the study through unsupervised learning classification. It is detailed in Section 3.1, and the overall process is illustrated in Figure 14 which provides a detailed flowchart of the methodology implemented in this study.

Figure 14: Flowchart of the Methodology for Data Clustering and MPC Optimization

As it is possible to see in the flowchart (Figure 14), the process involves several stages based on data preprocessing, the best dimensionality reduction by the autoencoders due to the iterative evaluation metrics, ensuring the best clustering results, and finally, the selection of representative days.

The second part of the methodology involves the analysis of the method transitioning from terminal-based to a unified system multiport converter detailed in Section 2.3.1. As it is possible to see in Figure 15, it is applied the same methodology as the iPlug project [4], with the differences of:

- The creation of a new scenario with new datasets (section 3.1.7).
- Specific configuration about the MPCs terminals and renewable generation (section 3.2).

- Total cost and optimization of the MPC

Figure 15: Flowchart of the MPC optimization process sizing methodology

According to the two parts defined in the project, the solid and consistent methodologies are determined to optimize multiport converters in hybrid energy systems with essential data profiles according to the representative days defined.

3.1 Data Clustering and Dimensionality reduction

As it has been mentioned in section 2.4, 2.4.1 and 2.4.2 the process of data clustering and dimensionality reduction is fundamental in this project in order to handle large datasets effectively, identify the representative elements and reduce the time computation of the process optimization of the MPC. Time-series aggregation consists of dimensionality reduction, simplifying the dataset, and maintaining the key features, making it feasible for the clustering algorithms k-means to group data effectively [59].

To establish the methodology for clustering and dimensionality reduction, the initial data utilized in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 originated from the iPLUG Project, specifically as part of Deliverable D1.2. This foundational dataset served as the basis for sensitivity analyses and the initial framework definition.

Building upon these results, a new scenario was developed, as outlined in section 3.1.7. This scenario incorporated new datasets designed to validate the scalability and applicability of the proposed methodology under different conditions. The use of the new scenario allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of the MPC optimization and system performance, ensuring its

adaptability to new datasets while maintaining consistency in the data format.

3.1.1 Data extraction and Preprocessing

The iPLUG Project provides dataset profiles used in this project as part of Deliverable D1.2 [4]. The dataset includes hourly profiles for solar, wind, and a year's consumption, forming the foundation for the clustering and dimensionality reduction analysis conducted in this part of the project.

Data preprocessing

The preprocessing of the datasets was performed using Python libraries for data manipulation. The libraries used were Pandas and Matplotlib to manipulate the data and facilitate exploratory data visualization. Initially, the raw Excel files were converted into Python data frames to facilitate the data processing and analysis.

Normalization Process

To ensure comparability between the three variables with different scales, the dataset was normalized by variable, enabling effective integration and comparison in future tasks. The normalization process adjusts each variable in range between 0 and 1, maintaining its relative distribution, preventing the domination in the clustering process from any single variable due to the magnitude [60]. The normalization was applied, following the next equation:

$$X_{norm} = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- X is the original value
- X_{min} is the minimum value of the variable
- X_{max} is the maximum value of the variable

Data analysis and quality assessment

After the normalization of the dataset, its quality was analyzed to ensure reliability and readiness for the clustering method. This process, it involves the potential issues that could affect to the quality of the analysis due to the distortion that can cause in the clustering results and the identification of representative days:

- **Missing values:** Not missing values were detected in the wind energy, solar energy, and consumption database.
- **Outliers:** Although some extreme values in wind energy were detected in Figure 16, they are considered as justifiable due to the high volatility in the nature of the data, such as wind energy production. These outliers reflect realistic scenarios rather than anomalies, preserving the integrity of the dataset
- **Duplicated values:** Not duplicated values were detected in the wind energy, solar energy, and consumption database.

To assess the quality and consistency of the dataset, an initial statistical analysis was conducted on the raw data to identify missing values, outliers, and duplicated values. This step ensures the reliability of the dataset and avoids potential distortions in the clustering results.

Table 1 presents the summary statistics for the dataset before normalization, highlighting the differences in scale between the variables, for instance, Consumption and PV. After applying the normalization process, the dataset's variables are scaled between 0 and 1, as shown in Table 2, ensuring comparability for clustering and dimensionality reduction tasks.

Table 1: Summary Statistics Before Normalization

	PV	WIND	Consumption
Count	8760	8760	8760
Mean	0.184456	0.219985	15964.361792
Std Dev	0.249458	0.223198	4435.831705
Min	0.0	0.0	3801.900000
25%	0.0	0.061000	12304.225000
50%	0.002000	0.140000	15613.650000
75%	0.382000	0.420000	19031.400000
Max	0.808000	0.991000	32350.500000

Table 2: Summary Statistics After Normalization

	PV	WIND	Consumption
Count	8736	8736	8736
Mean	0.182645	0.298834	0.352285
Std Dev	0.275386	0.237516	0.260538
Min	0.0	0.0	0.0
25%	0.0	0.106004	0.113064
50%	0.0	0.213250	0.253479
75%	0.402475	0.444044	0.532995
Max	1.0	1.0	1.0

Due to the normalization of the data, the Figure 16 and 17, show the boxplot and violin plots created to visualize the distribution and outliers as it is mentioned previously:

Figure 16: Boxplot of Normalized Variables

Figure 17: Violin Plot of Normalized Variables

Finally, these preprocessing processes ensure the reliability and consistency of the dataset quality.

3.1.2 Approaches for clustering classification and dimensionality reduction

According to the dataset's structure, different methods were applied for clustering classification, primarily focused on K-means, according to the application explained in section 2.4. Initially, the K-means algorithm was directly applied to the original dataset, experimenting with different configurations of the input data in terms of shape and dimensions.

Instead of arbitrarily selecting the number of clusters, an iterative approach was implemented. This approach systematically evaluated a range of cluster numbers with a predefined range,

calculating the metric of the Silhouette Score detailed in section 2.4.1 for each iteration. As it was mentioned in section 2.4.1, due to the complexity of determining the optimal number of clusters, the Silhouette Score was chosen as a robust measure of clustering quality, ensuring that the best number of clusters was selected based on the optimal balance between cluster separation and compactness.

Based on these configurations, different approaches were evaluated to improve the clustering quality of the representative days. To avoid arbitrary cluster selection, the iterative method ensures that the chosen clustering configuration reflects the clustering performance. The iterative methodology defined was applied consistently across the different configurations and dimensions of the input data, to compare the different results:

1. **Original Dataset clustering:** The structure used for this approach is a matrix of the 365 days with hourly data of every variable, analyzed every dataset for each variable wind energy, solar energy and consumption. Each variable was analyzed independently with a matrix of 365x24 according to each dataset. It was applied in order to establish a baseline for the clustering performance, evaluating the clustering quality for each variable separately and obtaining an upper limit for the clustering quality without any feature aggregation or dimensionality reduction.

Figure 18: Silhouette Scores for Individual Variables (Consumption, Wind, PV)

As it is obtained in Figure 18, the Silhouette Score evaluation of individual variables shows that the clustering quality depends on the variable analyzed. According to the three variables, Consumption, with the minimum number of clusters, achieves the highest silhouette Scores, ranging from 0.48 to 0.56, while PV exhibits the lowest scores due to its high number of zero values during non-generating hours.

The results also show that increasing the number of clusters means a reduction in the Silhouette Score metric, which indicates a decline in clustering quality as the data is split

into an excessive number of clusters. While the analysis of individual variables provides insights into the clustering quality for specific features, it does not account for potential interactions between variables. To address this, the next approach evaluates the clustering quality for bivariate combinations, aiming to uncover relationships between variables and improve the representation of the energy system's behavior.

2. **Bivariable feature aggregation:** According to the baseline established in the previous approach, it was considered the evaluation of the clustering quality with the structure of the dataset with a matrix of 365 rows (days) by 24 columns (hourly data) for pairs of variable, being the shape of every dataset of study 364x48. The possible combinations to analyze were wind-solar, wind-consumption, and solar-consumption. This approach was used with the aim of finding the key features and potential interactions between the variables, obtaining a more understandable representation of the profile of energy system behavior.

Figure 19: Silhouette Scores for Bivariate Combinations (Consumption-WIND, Consumption-PV, PV-WIND)

The figure 19 illustrates the Silhouette Scores obtained for the bivariate combinations of variables; among the combinations, Consumption-Wind achieves the highest scores, indicating better clustering quality and stronger interactions between these variables. Consumption-PV shows moderate clustering quality, while PV-Wind consistently exhibits the lowest scores, reflecting weaker relationships between these variables.

It is also evident that the Silhouette Score decreases as the number of clusters increases, as it happens in the previous approach. Additionally, the scores for the bivariate combinations are notably lower compared to the independent evaluation of each variable, indicating a reduction in clustering performance when combining variables. This highlights the trade-off between integrating more features to capture interactions and maintaining clustering quality.

3. **Multivariable feature aggregation:** With the results obtained from the previous approaches, this method combines the datasets of the three variables (wind energy, solar energy, and consumption) into a single dataset. Considering the overall energy system profile, the dataset is structured as a matrix of 365 rows (days of a year) by 72 columns (hourly data for all the variables combined).

The aim of this approach was to obtain the quality of clustering by integrating all the information available in the system, paying attention to the capture of complex relationships and correlations between the variables. However, aggregating all the variables into a single dataset significantly increases the size and dimensionality. The increment of the dataset was expected to challenge the reduction of clustering quality due to the high dimensionality of data. Specifically, problems such as reduced cluster separability and lower clustering quality metrics, including Silhouette Scores, were observed. These issues and limitations underscored the need for advanced dimensionality reduction techniques, detailed in section 2.4.2.

Figure 20: Silhouette Score with the combination of all the variables (Consumption/PV/Wind)

The Figure 20 illustrates the Silhouette Scores obtained with the consideration of all the variables, combining as a multivariable approach Consumption, Wind, and PV variables into a single dataset. The scores are significantly lower compared to those of individual variables or bivariate combinations, with the highest silhouette score in this specific case, approximately 0.26, for a small number of clusters.

This reduction in clustering quality reflects the challenges of high-dimensional datasets. The low Silhouette Scores observed in this approach confirm that the quality of the cluster is insufficient, being less than 0.5, as it was detailed in section 2.4.1 as a minimum result according to the bibliography to assure the compactness and quality of clusters, making it necessary to explore advanced dimensionality reduction techniques.

According to various configurations without dimensionality reduction, it was necessary to tackle the challenges associated with clustering in high-dimensional datasets, considering the metrics

results. Subsequently, the application of autoencoders for dimensionality reduction was analyzed, as detailed in section 3.1.4. This approach aimed to capture the patterns and identify the most relevant features of the representative days.

3.1.3 Transformation of the data and Splitting process

Data input transformation

In order to use machine learning methodologies effectively, such as Autoencoders, the input data must be preprocessed and structured correctly. After the normalization of numerical features in section 3.1.1 and reviewing the state Art for Convolutional Autoencoders in section 2.4.2 it is required specific format of input data according to assure compatibility with the layers in Convolutional Autoencoders, being (B,H,W,C) [61] where:

- **B (Batch size)**: Number of samples processed in each training iteration. Impacts on the computational efficiency and convergence of the model.
- **H (Height)**: Number of features per timestep.
- **W (Width)**: Number input dimensions or variables.
- **C (Channels)**: Means the depth of the input data.

The dataset used in this project has been structured to align with these requirements. Table 3 illustrates how the specific dimensions of $(365, 3, 24)$ correspond to the format (B, H, W, C) after preprocessing.

Table 3: Mapping Dataset to Convolutional Autoencoder Input Format

CAE Dimension	Value	Description of Dataset Mapping
B (Batch size)	365	Number of samples in the dataset, representing daily data for an entire year.
H (Height)	24	Number of features per timestep, corresponding to hourly data points in a day.
W (Width)	3	Number of input variables: wind energy, solar energy, and consumption.
C (Channels)	1	Depth of the input data. For this time-series dataset, a single channel is used to represent the data.

According to the nature of the data, being time-series data, the single channel $C=1$ is commonly used and treated as a single-dimensional spatial feature [62, 63]. The number of channels used according to the literature are:

- **C = 1**: Single-channel data such as grayscale images or single-variables time-series data.
- **C > 1**: Multichannel data, such as RGB images or datasets with multiple feature representations.

For this specific dataset, including three variables, to ensure compatibility with the convolu-

tional layers, the dataset is transformed from its initial shape of (365, 3, 24) to (365, 3, 24, 1) by adding a channel dimension using `np.expand_dims(data, axis=-1)`. It is appropriated as the data represents a single spatial feature over time.

After transforming the data input dimensions, the section 3.1.3 involves splitting the dataset into training, validation, and testing datasets for robust evaluation of the Convolutional Autoencoder.

Splitting process

The process of splitting data into three different groups is crucial for the evaluation of the machine-learning models in order to guarantee that the model is working well not only with the data that has been used to train but also with the new dataset provided to the model. Splitting data into three groups—training, validation, and testing—is crucial for evaluating machine learning models. This ensures the model performs well on the data used for training and new, unseen datasets. Here’s how these splits typically work [65]:

- **Training dataset (70%):** This is the largest portion of the data and is used to train the model. The model learns to recognize patterns and make predictions based on this dataset. It’s where the initial model weights and parameters are adjusted based on the feedback from the model’s performance.
- **Validation dataset (15%):** This dataset tunes the model parameters and prevents overfitting. It provides a reliable environment for fine-tuning model settings to optimize performance. The validation set is crucial for confirming that any improvements in the training phase actually translate to better generalization on new data.
- **Test dataset (15%):** After the model has been trained and validated, the test dataset provides the final measure of how well the model is expected to perform on external data. It is only used once, at the end of the modeling process, to assess the effectiveness and accuracy of the final model.

Adhering to this structured approach, can ensure that the model is robust, generalizes well to new data, and minimizes the risk of overfitting.

The dataset has been divided according to these proportions as it is possible to see in Table 4, summarizing the sizes and dimensions of each subset.

Table 4: Dataset Sizes After Splitting

Subset	Number of Samples	Shape
Training	292	(292, 3, 24, 1)
Validation	36	(36, 3, 24, 1)
Test	37	(37, 3, 24, 1)

3.1.4 Implementation of the Autoencoder

The autoencoder developed for this project is a neural network designed to encode and decode multivariate time-series data. It consists of two main parts: the **encoder**, which compresses the input into a latent representation, and the **decoder**, which reconstructs the original data from

this representation.

Autoencoder Architecture Design

Figure 21: Autoencoder Architecture

The following section explains each layer of the autoencoder, detailing its functionality and relevance within the data compression and reconstruction process.

This convolutional autoencoder is designed to process multivariate time-series data and reconstruct it from a compressed (latent) representation, according to the research defined in the State of Art of the Autoencoder section, which is detailed 2.4.2. The architecture is divided into two main parts: the **Encoder** and the **Decoder**. Below, each layer and its functionality are described.

Input Layer

- **Input dimensions:** (3, 24, 1), where:
 - 3: Represents the three variables (wind, solar, and consumption).
 - 24: Temporal features (hours per day).
 - 1: Channel dimension for univariate data.
- **Code:** `inputs = layers.Input(shape=input_shape)`
- **Function:** Initializes the model by defining the input data dimensions.

Encoder

The Encoder compresses the input data into a latent representation using convolutions and downsampling operations.

1. First Convolutional Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.Conv2D(16, (3, 3), activation="relu", padding="same")(inputs)`
- **Function:** Applies 16 filters of size 3×3 to extract local spatial-temporal features.
- **Justification:** Introduces non-linearity through ReLU activation and preserves dimensions using `padding="same"`.

2. First Max-Pooling Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.MaxPooling2D((1, 2), padding="same")(x)`
- **Function:** Reduces the horizontal resolution from 24 to 12.
- **Justification:** Compresses the data while retaining significant features, improving efficiency.

3. Second Convolutional Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.Conv2D(8, (3, 3), activation="relu", padding="same")(x)`
- **Function:** Refines the features extracted by the first convolutional layer using 8 filters.
- **Justification:** Reducing the number of filters focuses on essential patterns and prevents overfitting.

4. Second Max-Pooling Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.MaxPooling2D((1, 2), padding="same")(x)`
- **Function:** Further reduces the horizontal resolution from 12 to 6.
- **Justification:** Prepares the data for global pooling by condensing the information.

5. Global Max Pooling Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.GlobalMaxPooling2D()(x)`
- **Function:** Aggregates spatial features into a single one-dimensional vector.
- **Justification:** Reduces dimensionality, creating a compact representation for the latent layer.

6. Latent Layer (Dense):

- **Code:** `latent = layers.Dense(latent_dim, activation="sigmoid")(x)`
- **Function:** Encodes the compressed representation of the input into a vector of size `latent_dim`.
- **Justification:** Acts as the bottleneck of the autoencoder, capturing the most critical features of the input.

Decoder

The Decoder reconstructs the original input from the latent representation.

1. First Dense Layer and Reshape:

- **Code:** `x = layers.Dense(3 * 6 * 8, activation='relu')(latent)`
`x = layers.Reshape((3, 6, 8))(x)`

- **Function:** Expands the latent representation and reshapes it into a spatial format.
- **Justification:** Prepares the data for further reconstruction using transposed convolutions.

2. First Transposed Convolutional Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.Conv2DTranspose(8, (3, 3), strides=(1, 2), activation='relu', padding='same')(x)`
- **Function:** Upsamples the horizontal resolution from 6 to 12.
- **Justification:** Gradually restores the original dimensions while maintaining feature quality.

3. Second Transposed Convolutional Layer:

- **Code:** `x = layers.Conv2DTranspose(16, (3, 3), strides=(1, 2), activation='relu', padding='same')(x)`
- **Function:** Upsamples the horizontal resolution from 12 to 24, reaching the original dimensions.
- **Justification:** Ensures the reconstructed data aligns with the original input size.

4. Output Layer:

- **Code:** `decoded = layers.Conv2DTranspose(1, (3, 3), activation='sigmoid', padding='same')(x)`
- **Function:** Produces the final reconstructed output with dimensions (3, 24, 1).
- **Justification:** The sigmoid activation ensures normalized values between 0 and 1, matching the preprocessed input.

Model Compilation

- **Code:** `autoencoder.compile(optimizer=optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=0.001), loss=MeanSquaredError())`
- **Function:** Configures the model for training using the Adam optimizer and MeanSquaredError loss function.
- **Justification:** The Adam optimizer dynamically adapts to gradients for efficient learning, while MeanSquaredError penalizes reconstruction errors to improve accuracy.

3.1.5 Selecting the Best Autoencoder and Clustering Configuration

This section explores the integration of the Autoencoder architecture defined in section 3.1.4 with the K-means algorithm used in the first approaches for clustering classification in section 3.1.2 as a baseline of the clustering classification.

According to the dimensions and the different variables of the dataset, the main objective is to utilize the latent space representation in 3D in order to improve the clustering classification, using the evaluation metrics and the visual graphics for the justification of the performance of the model.

According to the dimensionality reduction capabilities of the Autoencoder, it is possible to evaluate the correct codification and de-codification of the data, ensuring that the input data with the main structure defined in section 3.1.3 is represented in the latent space preserving the key features, and how has been mentioned before in 3D, allowing the user to see the different points of the data with dimensionality reduction. Then, K-Means clustering is applied to the reduced latent space, effectively grouping the codification data, identifying patterns, and grouping similar data points.

Benchmark MSE: Predicting the Average

The benchmark MSE model is a simple and base approach that predicts the mean value of the target variable for all inputs. It is typically used in order to evaluate the performance of other complex models as the Autoencoder.

- **No assumptions about spatial or temporal patterns:** It assumes no knowledge about spatial or temporal patterns and basically predicts the average value across the dataset.
- **Baseline for improvement:** the benchmark MSE establishes a lower bound for model performance. It provides a clear standard to measure the added value of more advanced models like the autoencoder.
- **Justification results Autoencoder:** Comparing the MSE of the autoencoder with the benchmark, it provides added value with significant improvement. A significant reduction in MSE demonstrates the efficiency and effectiveness of the autoencoder in capturing spatial and temporal dependencies and correlation in the data.

In order to ensure the autoencoder provides a useful improvement compared with the benchmark, it has been established at least a threshold of 50%. This threshold guarantees that the selected autoencoder model offers a substantial improvement, making the difference due to the complexity of the model.

Figure 22: Flowchart of Baseline Mean Squared Error (MSE) Calculation.

The flowchart above illustrates the process of calculating the MSE benchmark by predicting the mean of the training data for the test set. This benchmark is then compared to the autoencoder's performance to evaluate the improvement.

Benchmark Silhouette Score

As explained in section 3.1.2, the Silhouette Score is a robust measure of clustering quality, evaluating the compactness and the separation between clusters. For this study, a minimum threshold is established of 0.4 in order to ensure the reliability and meaningfulness of the clustering results [53].

3.1.6 Selection of Representative Days

According to the fundament of the algorithm K-means detailed in section 2.4.1, it is obtained the centroid of every cluster, and is grouping the data points based on their proximity. The centroid is the most representative value of the cluster calculated as the mean of all data points within the cluster, moreover, the algorithm minimizes the sum of squared distances between the centroids and the data points through iterations [66].

It is for the mentioned before, the data which is more close to the centroid of each cluster, it can be considered as the best representation of the cluster due to the following reasons:

- Proximity to the Average of the data: The centroid represents the average of all data points in a cluster, and the closest point to it is the most similar to this average.
- Minimal Variability: The nearest point to the centroid minimizes the differences with the cluster's center.
- Practical Relevance in Time-series Analysis: In time-series data, selecting the point closest to the centroid ensures it captures the dominant patterns.

The selection of representative days is established by defining the centroids mentioned.

3.1.7 Creation of a New Scenario

After considering the validation of the functionality and effectiveness of the optimization process for dimensionality reduction and clustering methodology using external data provided by the iPLUG project [4], the next step involved is the design of a different scenario with new datasets. This dataset maintained the same variables and data structure as the external dataset to ensure consistency in the analysis and comparability of results.

The main objective of this section is to evaluate the flexibility and scalability of the defined methodology of figure 14 when it is applied to different datasets. By creating this new scenario, the study demonstrates how the proposed methodology adapts to specific energy profiles and explores its potential generalization to other case studies.

Extraction of the data

The new scenario was created using publicly available solar photovoltaic (PV), wind, and load profiles datasets. As mentioned before, the datasets maintained the same structure and variables as those used in the iPLUG deliverable, ensuring consistency in the analysis process.

- **Load profile:** The load profile used for this project was extracted from **ELMAS dataset** [67]. this dataset provides hourly electrical load profiles for 18 industrial and tertiary sectors in France. This dataset is based on an aggregation of 55,730 time series corresponding to 424 business sectors, classified according to the NACE standard (Statistical Classification of Economic Activities). As it is explained in the paper [67], for privacy reasons, the initial time series were anonymized and clustered using K-means to group businesses with similar temporal consumption patterns into 18 representative clusters. Due to confidentiality restrictions, the ELMAS dataset was selected as a reliable and comprehensive source due to the reduced availability of the public data load for the industrial and tertiary sectors and the variety of the 18 different profiles. Its variety of 18 different load profiles provides sufficient granularity and diversity to construct realistic load scenarios. For this project, the load profile was chosen based on the similarity of magnitude and temporal patterns to the original data used in the iPLUG deliverable [4]. The selection of the load profile, based on its alignment with the magnitude and variability observed in the original iPLUG dataset, ensures consistency with the initial analysis while capitalizing on the detailed granularity and diversity offered by the ELMAS dataset
- **Solar photovoltaic and wind power generation profile:** the profile of renewables was obtained from the platform RENEWABLE NINJA [68]. This platform provides hourly power availability for 1 kW of wind power and 1kWp of PV power installed, based on meteorological and solar radiation data for specific locations. For this specific project, generation profiles were extracted for the only available year, 2019, representing typical power availability in the region of interest. The location chosen was France to maintain the dataset's consistency with the publicly available load profiles obtained from this region, ensuring a coherent scenario for analysis.

This approach follows the methodology outlined in the original iPLUG report [4], ensuring that power availability is consistent across the selected area.

3.1.8 Comparison between Original and New Scenario

The comparison is focused specifically on the load profiles to ensure the similarity in magnitude and variability, which is critical to maintaining the consistency of performance of the future methodology applied for the MPC. The 18 clusters represent different load profiles from the ELMAS, as mentioned in subsection 3.1.7, and were evaluated to identify the most similar profile to the original iPLUG dataset. The following methodology ensures that the new scenario does not deviate significantly from the baseline study.

Although the wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) generation profiles were extracted from the same platform as in the original study, they were not directly compared. This is because these profiles are independent and tailored to represent the geographical and meteorological conditions of the selected region in France, ensuring consistency and relevance for the new scenario without requiring further validation.

Methodology for Comparison

1. Selection of Metrics and identification of the most similar profile

A metric is needed in order to quantify the similarity of the datasets. The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) [70] was chosen as the primary metric because it normalizes the error, allowing fair comparisons between profiles with different magnitudes. Moreover, MAPE provides an intuitive percentage-based evaluation, making it particularly suitable for this specific comparison between load profiles.

However, it is important to note that this metric is highly sensitive to outliers due to the reliance on the actual observed value (y_i) in the denominator, but, despite of this limitation, It remains a valid and effective choice in this case, as a main goal to discard clusters with profiles significantly different from the original dataset, rather than achieving precise error measurements.

The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) was calculated for each of the 18 load profiles available in the ELMAS dataset. Its components are defined as follows:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (3)$$

- y_i : Actual observed values.
- \hat{y}_i : Predicted or estimated values.
- n : Total number of observations.
- $|\cdot|$: Absolute value operator.
- $\times 100$: Converts the result into a percentage.

The MAPE values for all 18 clusters were then represented in a bar chart to visualize the comparison results:

Figure 23: MAPE Values for the 18 Load Clusters

Figure 23 exhibits that Cluster 18 has the lowest MAPE (30.72%), the most similar load profile to the iPLUG dataset. The other clusters shown in blue have significantly higher MAPE values, reflecting their lower alignment with the original profile, which is out of the case of study or future scenarios.

2. Graphical Analysis

It was possible to represent graphically the dataset of cluster 18 and the original load profile (iPLUG)

Figure 24: Comparison of Original and Selected Cluster (18) Load Profiles over the year

The graph illustrates the superposition of the original load profile (iPLUG) and Cluster 18, which was selected based on MAPE over the course of a year. Both profiles exhibit similar consumption patterns and follow the same seasonal trends, with peaks and troughs aligning with fluctuations in energy demand throughout the year.

While minor local differences exist in the magnitude of the load, they do not significantly impact the overall similarity between the profiles. The general shape of high-demand peaks and low-demand periods remains consistent across both profiles, another visual validation for selecting cluster 18 as the most appropriate representative profile for the new analysis scenario.

3. Statistical Representation

Figure 25: Frequency Distribution of iPLUG and Cluster 18 Load Profiles

Figure 26: Boxplot Comparison of iPLUG and Cluster 18 Load Profiles

Figures 25 and 26 shown a statistical comparison between the original iPLUG load profile and Cluster 18. The histogram (Figure 25) shows that both datasets have a quite similar distribution, with overlapping areas and ranges of Load values. The boxplot (Figure 26) highlights that the spread, median and overall distribution of load values are consistent between the two datasets, confirming the alignment and the validity of the data selected.

The analysis and methodology defined to determine the new load profile for a new scenario demonstrate that cluster 18 is the most representative load profile when compared to the original iPLUG dataset. The metrics and graphical and statistical validation combination confirm the similarity patterns, distribution, and seasonal trends. Thanks to that it is defined a strong basis for selecting cluster 18 to construct the new analysis scenario and proceed with further modeling and optimization.

3.2 Definition of the New Sizing Methodology MPCs

According to the original methodology detailed in the State of Art, section 2.3.1 (Terminal-based approach) and the new methodology proposed by different papers in section 2.3.1 (Ensemble-Based MPC), it is presented the new methodology defined for sizing the MPCs.

The network data, such as the lines and topology used in this case of study, **are the same as the one used in the iPLUG project [69]**, which is based on the IEEE 33 bus system. The system is 12.66 kV with one feeder substation and 33 buses, with an MPC with four terminals connected to two AC buses (12, 22) and two DC buses (34, 35) injecting renewable energy into the grid.

Figure 27: Grid topology of 33 bus with MPC of four terminals case study

The hourly profiles of load, PV, and Wind are defined in section 3.1.7; moreover, the distribution in the buses considered are taken from the iPLUG project [4].

The equation of the grid model, the process of single-day optimization, and the overall joint optimization framework of the grid problem (considering equality and inequality constraints) are considered the same as the iPLUG project [4] and [10] detailed in the State of Art section 2.3.1.

3.2.1 Renewables sizing

According to the hourly data and power distribution considered from the original scenario explained previously, the power installed of renewable energy considering wind and PV, has been 50% of the branch with the highest power consumption:

Bus Group	Total Active Power (kW)	50% in Renewables (kW)
Buses 19/20/21/22	360	180
Buses 23/24/25	930	465
Buses 26/27/28/29/30/31/32/33	920	460

Table 5: Summary of Total Active Power and 50% in Renewables by Bus Group

As it is possible to see in Table 5, the power installed of renewable energy has been 465 kW for each type of energy, Wind and PV, following the distribution shown in Figure 32 in the nodes 34 and 35 connected to the MPC. Finally, renewable are defined as:

ID	Type	Bus	Installed Power [kW]
1	PV	34	465
2	Wind	35	465

Table 6: Summary of Renewable Energy Sources

3.2.2 Proposed methodology MPC

This section details the aim of the second part of the project, which is to transition from terminal-based sizing optimization of MPC to ensemble-based MPC optimization. As it is detailed in the State of Art in section 2.3, the original methodology is focused on sizing each terminal separately, and the proposed ensemble-based optimization design of the entire MPC system considers every single terminal in the optimization. The changes implemented in the Python block named "Multiport" are:

1. Redefinition of Aparent Power Initialization

(a) Original Optimization:

In the original implementation, the nominal apparent power S_n is defined independently for each terminal:

$$S_n(i_{\text{terminal}}) \quad \forall i_{\text{terminal}} \in l_{\text{terminal}}$$

Each terminal operates within its own predefined limit, with no connection to other terminals.

(b) Global MPC Optimization:

In the new implementation, a hierarchy is introduced:

i. Global Nominal Capacity for the MPC:

$$S_n(i_{\text{MPC}}) \quad \forall i_{\text{MPC}} \in l_{\text{MPC}}$$

ii. Individual Apparent Power of Terminals:

$$S(i_{\text{terminal}}, t) \quad \forall i \in l_{\text{terminal}}, \forall t \in l_t$$

Each terminal's apparent power must satisfy the following condition:

$$\sum_{i_{\text{terminal}} \in l_{\text{terminal}}} S(i_{\text{terminal}}, t) \leq S_n(i_{\text{MPC}}) \quad \forall t \in l_t$$

In the original implementation, the nominal apparent power (S_n) is defined for each terminal individually. This means each terminal is optimized independently as a variable, with no direct relationship to other terminals.

In the new implementation, two variables are introduced: the nominal apparent power of the entire converter ($S_n(i_{\text{MPC}})$), which is optimized as a global component, and the apparent power of each terminal ($S(i_{\text{terminal}}, t)$), which is calculated at each time step based

on the system's conditions. This approach allows the terminals to adjust dynamically and be optimized according to all the terminals connected to the MPC.

2. Active Power Balancing

In the original methodology, the active power for each terminal was already defined individually, ensuring that the contributions of each terminal to the overall system were explicitly taken into account. According to the active power balance, which is the principle of net power balance zero and has to be respected within the different methodologies, it is possible to maintain the original definition to ensure that the equality constraint is satisfied.

$$\sum_{i \in l_{\text{terminal}}} P(i_{\text{terminal}}, t) = 0 \quad \forall t \in l_t \quad (4)$$

3. Current Limits

AC Case:

$$I(i_{\text{port}}, t)^2 \cdot V(b, t)^2 = P(i_{\text{port}}, t)^2 + Q(i_{\text{port}}, t)^2$$

This relationship applies to both the original and the global formulations, ensuring that the RMS current times the bus voltage corresponds to the active and reactive power components.

DC Case:

$$\pm P(i_{\text{port}}, t) \leq I(i_{\text{port}}, t)$$

In DC configurations, the main focus is the active power P being bounded by the current I .

Original Approach (Per-Terminal):

$$I(i_{\text{port}}, t) \leq I_{\text{max}}(i_{\text{port}}) \implies I(i_{\text{port}}, t) \leq S_n(i_{\text{port}})$$

Each terminal is capped by its own rated current (or nominal power S_n), preventing any sharing of unused capacity among terminals. This can lead to overdimensioning if peak demands do not coincide.

Global MPC Approach:

$$\sum_{i_{\text{port}}} I(i_{\text{port}}, t) \leq I_{\text{max}}(i_{\text{MPC}}) \implies \sum_{i_{\text{port}}} I(i_{\text{port}}, t) \leq S_n(i_{\text{MPC}})$$

Instead of limiting each terminal independently, the total current (or total power) across all terminals connected to one MPC is constrained by the MPC's aggregate capacity. This allows terminals to share headroom, reducing the chance of overdimensioning and increasing the system's flexibility.

4. Reactive Power limits

The reactive power limits for the MPC are defined based on IEEE Standard 1547, which requires energy storage DER to support a reactive power exchange of $\pm 44\%$, corresponding to a power factor of 0.915. These constraints ensure that the MPC operates within its

nominal apparent power capacity, avoiding oversizing and inefficiencies as it can see in the following Figure 28

Figure 28: Reactive constraints of MPC [4]

(a) **Original Reactive Power Limits:**

- Each **converter** was independently constrained to respect the reactive power limit ($\pm 44\%$) of its nominal apparent power. The constraints for the upper and lower bounds were defined as:

$$Q_{\text{conv}}(i_{\text{conv}}, t) \leq 0.44 \cdot S_n(i_{\text{terminal}}) \cdot V(i, t)$$

$$-Q_{\text{conv}}(i_{\text{conv}}, t) \leq 0.44 \cdot S_n(i_{\text{terminal}}) \cdot V(i, t)$$

- These constraints ensure that the reactive power exchanged by each converter does not exceed the IEEE 1547-defined limits relative to the nominal apparent power scaled by voltage V (Figure 28).
- **Disadvantage:** The reactive power for each converter was treated in isolation, meaning there was no consideration of shared capacity or dynamic reallocation between converters.

(b) **Global MPC optimization:**

- The new implementation introduces **global constraints** by aggregating the reactive power across all converters connected to the same **MPC**. The upper and lower bounds for the reactive power are now expressed as:

$$\sum_{i \in I_{\text{conv}}} Q_{\text{conv}}(i, t) \leq 0.44 \cdot S_n(i_{\text{MPC}})$$

$$\sum_{i \in l_{\text{conv}}} -Q_{\text{conv}}(i, t) \leq 0.44 \cdot S_n(i_{\text{MPC}})$$

- The constraints now aggregate the reactive power across all connected converters while normalizing for the voltage and excluding any DC-connected buses from the calculation.
- **Dynamic Capacity Sharing:** By incorporating all converters linked to the same **MPC**, the new approach allows for shared reactive power limits. This ensures better resource utilization and prevents individual converters from being unnecessarily constrained.

(c) Cost of MPCs

The cost of the original methodology of the **MPCs** is defined according to the sum of the capacity of every terminal connected to the **MPCs** multiplied by the cost in units €/kVA.

The new methodology directly considers the total **MPC** size multiplied by the cost in €/kVA, due to the optimization as a whole and not by the terminal.

It is considered the same price as the original methodology:

Parameters	Base value	Additional values
Converter cost	150 €/kVA	140, 160 €/kVA

Table 7: Converter costs derived from the original methodology. [4]

3.2.3 Optimization problem

As it was mentioned before, the methodology of optimization is based on iPLUG project [4] and [10]

The objective function is mathematically expressed as:

$$[\min] f_{\text{obj}} = -I_{\text{ren}} \cdot k_{\text{renewables}} + E_{\text{loss}} \cdot C_{\text{loss}} \cdot t_{\text{life}} + C_{\text{MPC}} + \text{Other} \quad (5)$$

- Where $k_{\text{renewables}}$ is a coefficient set to 1.2 in this case, acting as a weighting factor in the objective function to prioritize renewable energy production. This coefficient directly incentivizes the integration of renewable sources into the system, ensuring that the optimization process supports increased renewable participation while maintaining operational efficiency and minimizing overall system costs.
- The renewable income (I_{ren}) is calculated based on the total energy generated by renewable sources and the electricity market price:

$$I_{\text{ren}} = 365 \cdot \sum_{i \in l_{\text{renew}}} \sum_{t \in l_t} P_{\text{renew}}(i, t) \cdot \text{price}_{\text{buy}}(t)$$

where:

- I_{ren} : Total annual income from renewable energy generation [€].
- $P_{\text{renew}}(i, t)$: Energy generated by renewable source i at time t [kW].
- $\text{price}_{\text{buy}}(t)$: Market price for electricity purchase at time t considered as 50 [€/kWh].
- l_{renew} : Set of all renewable energy sources in the system.
- l_t : Set of all time intervals considered in the analysis.
- 365: Multiplier to calculate annual income from daily values.

This equation represents the annual income derived from renewable energy sources, ensuring the energy generated is monetized based on market prices.

- The C_{loss} considered are €0.1867 per KWh, considered the European Union average price in the first half of 2024 for non-household consumers[73], and the lifetime of the project about 20 years, which is the lifetime of the MPCs [4].
- The "Other" term is related to the penalization of significant voltage deviations, promoting system stability and ensuring operation within acceptable voltage ranges.

$$\text{Other} = \frac{\Delta V_{\text{tot}}}{4} \quad (6)$$

4 Results

This section is divided into two parts: Clustering Results of the New Scenario and MCP's results.

4.1 Dimensionality reduction and clustering Results New Scenario

This section detailed the clustering results of the methodology defined in section 3.1 with the new scenario created according to section 3.1.7.

After 50 iterations and analysis of each iteration, the number of clusters obtained was between 6 and 15, according to the following results:

Table 8: Best results of Cluster obtained

Metric	Results
Silhouette Score	0.4164
MSE General	0.012027
Number of Clusters	13

Table 8 shows that the best number of clusters is 13. This number leads to a low Silhouette Score and MSE, thus it guarantees, which are the groups in which the data can be grouped, determined by the threshold defined and the best combination of Silhouette Score and MSE of the representation of the input data by the codification done by the Autoencoder.

After the results obtained from the first approaches detailed in section 3.1.2 and the definition of the different range of Silhouette Score in section 2.4.1, the compactness and the quality of the clusters could be considered as a moderate.

Despite being different data due to the creation of a new scenario, the load profile, solar photovoltaic, and wind production had a similar distribution compared to the original data used for the first approaches with only K-means. Comparing the results of Silhouette Score has been increased by around 0.2 with more number of clusters in order to have better analysis and approach of the optimization of the MPCs, according to figure 20 where the maximum Silhouette Score possible to achieve was 0.26 with 5 clusters.

Number of Clusters	Original Method (5 clusters, Silhouette 0.26)	New Method (13 clusters, Silhouette 0.4164)
Optimal Clusters	5 Clusters	13 Clusters
Silhouette Coefficient	0.26	0.4164

Table 9: Comparison between the original and new methods .

Due to the high dimensionality in the latent space of the original method’s data difficulties the visualization of the different clusters. However, according to the codification of the data by the Autoencoder in a 3 dimensions vector , it was possible to extract the best representation obtained by the results and visualize the different clusters of the dataset in the latent space.

Figure 29: Latent Space representation with the Autoencoder codification

As it is possible to see in the latent space representation in Figure 29, the different groups of the data are clearly defined, making the differentiation of the representative days possible. This is a visual and intuitive method to validate the grouping process of the data and the selection of representative days. This visualization supports the validation of the methodology defined in section 3.1 and enhances the interpretability of the results in a

visual way. The challenge of data visualization for the dataset with high dimensionality reduction has been solved with this application.

In order to measure the importance of the results obtained by the Autoencoder, it was compared with a Base model only taking into account the average in the test data as it was explained in section 3.1.5:

Figure 30: Comparison of MSE between Autoencoder and Base model

It is possible to see in Figure 30 the comparison of the MSE between the Autoencoder and the Base model applied to the test data. The MSE obtained by the Autoencoder was significantly lower compared to the base model. This result supports the idea that the Autoencoder is more effective in representing new data not seen before by the model and capturing patterns, providing a more accurate reconstruction. The improvement of the MSE by the Autoencoder compared with the Base model is 66.56% , representing a substantial reduction in error and the justification of the use of this model obtained after different iterations.

Then, after the comparison of the base model and the Autoencoder, it is possible to see in Figure 31 the work flow that is following the model as the example of the State of Art Figure 12:

Figure 31: Autoencoder Architecture: Compression and Reconstruction Process

The Autoencoder is compressing the input data into a 3D latent space vector, as it is defined in the methodology, and it is possible to reconstruct the output data with minimal differences. This process demonstrates the ability of the model to capture the key features and patterns, even in a reduced-dimensional representation.

It is important to note that Figure 31 represents only one example from the test dataset. Each example in the dataset is unique and can show different levels of reconstruction accuracy depending on the nature of the data. Some inputs are reconstructed with more level of accuracy, this variability is expected given the nature and characteristics of the Autoencoder model.

Further details and additional clustering results can be found in section 9 (Appendix A) with the figures 44, 45, 46, and 47, which illustrates examples of the input data, their latent space representations, and their reconstructed outputs. This section of the Appendix gives a specific example of 4 days, demonstrating the results of the process transformation of the input data into the encoded data and the reconstruction form of the data. It can be seen that depending on the nature of the data, some examples are reconstructed with lower errors than others, being expected due to the nature of this type of model.

Then, after obtaining the clusters and confirming the effectiveness and results obtained by the model, the representative days were selected according to the distance from the centroids of each cluster, which are the most representative of the data as detailed in section 3.1.6. The representative days selected are:

These representative days are the days used for the analysis of the different methodologies of optimization of the MPCs detailed in section 3.2. Due to the capture of the key patterns and features of the data, it represents a consistent analysis for the MPC framework.

Cluster	Representative Day	Weight
1	04-01-2019	7.7%
2	13-01-2019	7.7%
3	20-01-2019	7.7%
4	23-01-2019	7.7%
5	15-02-2019	7.7%
6	10-03-2019	7.7%
7	04-05-2019	7.7%
8	26-07-2019	7.7%
9	12-08-2019	7.7%
10	07-09-2019	7.7%
11	11-09-2019	7.7%
12	15-09-2019	7.7%
13	28-11-2019	7.7%

Table 10: Results of Clusters, their Representative Days, and Weights

Figure 32: Load and Generation profile of 33 bus case study Representative days

As is illustrated in Figure 32, the 13 representative days are relevant due to the differences across the different days, capturing the key features and the patterns of the data created in the new scenario.

Further details and additional illustrations of the representative days are presented in section 9 (Appendix A). These graphics illustrate the consumption profile, solar photovoltaic, and wind generation, demonstrating the different ranges of values and variability across the different clusters obtained, with differences in their daily patterns. This variability is crucial for evaluating and optimizing the MPCs methods, ensuring that the analysis and results capture the different key features and behaviors of the whole dataset.

In order to complement the analysis and visualization of the daily patterns across the different clusters, normalized boxplots were generated for each variable and cluster inde-

pendently. This allows clear visualization of the different distributions by variable and cluster, for a more detailed comparison:

Figure 33: Comparison of Normalized Variable Distributions Across Clusters

The boxplot of Figure 33 shows the normalized variable distributions across the variables PV, wind generation, and load consumption. The distributions have huge variability, reflecting the diversity captured by the different representative days. As shown in the previous data analysis in section 3.1.1, the solar photovoltaic generation exhibits a high number of outliers in all the clusters due to the nature of the data, which is aligned with the dependence on external factors as weather conditions. These clusters support the importance of considering these data as the best approach for the optimization analysis.

Furthermore, in section 9 (Appendix A) are illustrated in Figures 55, 56 and 57, the different boxplots of each variable separately without the normalization of the data in order to visualize the different distribution across the different clusters, being the high differences between the representative days confirming the quality and correlation of the same cluster and the differences between them.

According to the Silhouette Score, the MSE obtained in the reconstruction of the data, visual validation methods such as the latent space representation, the similar distribution within the same cluster, and the different distributions between clusters in the variables considered, it can be confirmed that the results obtained from the dimensionality reduction and the clustering methodology, is suitable to capture the variability of the dataset.

This ensures that the key patterns are well represented in the representative days in order to establish a framework to create reduced datasets for implementing optimization strategies through MPC reducing the time computation. Additionally, due to the methodology established, it can be extended to datasets with similar features, dimensionality, and variables, offering a scalable and adaptable solution for future analysis and optimization needs.

4.2 MPC Results and Comparative Analysis

This section presents the analysis and comparison of the results obtained with the original and new methodologies applied for sizing the MPCs, detailed in section 2.3. The analysis was conducted using the representative days obtained from the dimensionality reduction and clustering results in section 4.1.

To ensure an accurate comparison, the same network topology, dataset, constraints (inequality and equality), grid definition, and objective function were maintained for both methodologies. This approach allows for a detailed analysis of the most relevant variables and highlights the improvements introduced by the updated methodology. The primary difference between the two approaches lies in the sizing process of the multiport converter, as explained in section 3.2.2, and the role of renewable generation in the system based on the installed capacity.

Considering the project’s objective, the optimization process of sizing the MPCs capacity resulted in the following results for the two methodologies:

Figure 34: Grid topology and results of the original methodology for MPC capacity

Figure 35: Grid topology and results of the modified methodology for MPC capacity

As is shown in Figure 34 and 35, the number of ports and connections is maintained in order to analyze the changes in the sizing and the behavior under the same conditions. It is possible to observe, in the first figure, the sizing has been made by terminal, without having relation between the terminals, and the capacity of the terminal, the maximum apparent power demanded in a certain period of time taking into account the objective function. The second figure has been sized according to the maximum apparent power in a certain period of time, but considering the interconnection and balance between the different terminals of the MPCs, it can be reduced according to the flexibility provided by the optimization.

Figure 36: Comparison of MPC capacity across the different methodologies

According to the new methodology, the MPC is sized at 1243.14 kVA, while the original methodology sizes the MPC per terminal, resulting in a total capacity of 1721 kVA when summing the terminal capacities (Figure 36). This represents a reduction of approximately 28%, which directly impacts the cost of the MPC, as the cost is closely tied to its capacity. This comparison highlights the oversizing introduced by the original methodology.

To gain a better understanding beyond the reduction in MPC sizing and the avoidance of oversizing, it is crucial to consider the conditions under which the two scenarios operate in relation to renewable energy production. These conditions influence how the system integrates and manages the variability of wind and photovoltaic generation, as well as the interaction between terminals and the grid.

Figure 37: Comparison of Renewable power generation across the different methodologies

As observed in Figure 37, the photovoltaic and wind power generation are associated with terminals 3 and 4. Considering these connections and the absence of reactive power due to the DC nature of these buses, the active power directly corresponds to the apparent power. An important point to highlight is the limitation in renewable generation (both photovoltaic and wind) observed in the original methodology compared to the new one. With an installed capacity of 50% of the branch's maximum load power (456 kW), the original methodology seems to impose a generation of approximately 300 kWh for wind and 290 kWh for photovoltaic energy. In contrast, the new methodology allows for greater renewable generation, which is particularly noticeable at these maximum points, where significant peaks are reached.

A clear conclusion is that the new methodology, driven by the optimization function, prioritizes renewable energy generation while balancing the cost of the converter. In the original methodology, increasing the capacity of terminals 3 and 4 to accommodate higher renewable generation is not considered cost-effective, resulting in the observed generation curtailment.

Once the active power generated by the renewable energies connected to terminals 3 and 4 of the MPC has been analyzed, the apparent power of each terminal has been analyzed for the two defined methodologies:

Figure 38: Comparison Apparent power capacity by terminal across the different methodologies

As observed in Figure 38, the comparison between the original and modified methodologies for apparent power (S_{MPC}) highlights key differences in the behavior of the system,

particularly across the terminals. Terminals 3 and 4, connected to DC buses, do not have reactive power due to their direct connection to renewable energy sources (wind and photovoltaic generation). As a result, the apparent power in these terminals corresponds directly to the active power generated, as depicted in Figure 37, and reflects the renewable generation behavior already analyzed.

In the total apparent power comparison, it becomes evident that the modified methodology reduces peak values and optimizes the usage of the MPC. This is crucial for minimizing oversizing while still meeting system demands. The fluctuations in the original methodology, with higher peaks and less consistent operation, underline the inefficiencies that result from sizing the MPC per terminal rather than as a unified system. The modified approach, on the other hand, smoothens the power demand curve, allowing for a more efficient allocation of the converter's capacity.

Terminals 1 and 2 show notable differences in power demand between the two methodologies. Higher peaks can be observed in the original methodology, indicating a lack of coordination between terminals. This leads to moments of overutilization and redundancy in capacity. The modified methodology, by optimizing the MPC holistically, balances the power requirements across these terminals, reducing unnecessary peaks and ensuring a more stable operation.

For terminals 3 and 4, the differences between the methodologies are less pronounced, as renewable generation directly dictates the apparent power demand. However, the modified methodology allows for slightly higher peak values in Terminal 3, demonstrating its ability to accommodate periods of high renewable generation without oversizing the converter. Terminal 4 maintains similar profiles in both methodologies, as the wind power generation remains relatively stable.

Overall, this figure emphasizes the benefits of the modified methodology in achieving a more efficient system design. By considering the total apparent power and optimizing the sizing process, the modified approach reduces the MPC's capacity requirements while maintaining or improving its ability to handle renewable energy integration. This minimizes costs and ensures a more reliable and balanced power system operation. The differences in Terminals 1 and 2 highlight the inefficiencies of the original methodology, while the consistent performance in Terminals 3 and 4 underscores the compatibility of the modified approach with renewable energy integration.

Under the framework of this analysis, after examining the renewable power generated by terminals 3 and 4 and subsequently analyzing the apparent power of each terminal for both methodologies, attention is now turned to the behavior of reactive power (Q_{MPC}). As previously noted, in terminals 3 and 4, which are connected to DC buses, the apparent power directly corresponds to the active power due to the absence of reactive power. This provides a clear reference point for validating the consistency and accuracy of the two methodologies. Meanwhile, the reactive power in terminals 1 and 2 plays a critical role in maintaining system stability, offering valuable insights into how the original and modified methodologies differ in their management strategies.

The results of the reactive power comparison for each terminal under both methodologies are shown in Figure 40. This figure provides a detailed view of the reactive power

trends, allowing us to identify key differences and draw meaningful conclusions about the performance of each approach.

Figure 39: Comparison of Reactive power by terminal across the different methodologies

The figure highlights distinct differences between the methodologies in reactive power management. For terminals 1 and 2, the modified methodology displays significant variations and higher peaks in reactive power over time. These fluctuations suggest that, despite achieving overall system efficiency, the modified approach requires a more dynamic

response at these terminals to optimize power allocation. In contrast, the original methodology exhibits a much smoother and more stable reactive power profile for terminals 1 and 2. Peaks are consistently lower, and the demand remains more uniform over time, reflecting a more conservative allocation of reactive power resources. However, this stability in the original approach may come at the cost of less efficient system-wide performance.

The results of terminals 3 and 4 connected to DC buses align with expectations: reactive power is virtually negligible in both methodologies. The modified methodology accurately maintains this absence of reactive power, with no fluctuations observed throughout the time steps. Meanwhile, the original methodology shows minor deviations, likely due to numerical resolution, as the values are lower than the tolerance specification of the optimization.

Figure 40: Reactive power comparison by terminals and the grid

Although terminals 1 and 2 in the modified methodology exhibit higher reactive power peaks and fluctuations compared to the original approach (as observed in their temporal reactive power graphs), the cumulative analysis of reactive power exchanged with the main grid provides a more comprehensive perspective on system efficiency. This cumulative view highlights a key conclusion:

The modified methodology achieves greater efficiency in the overall reactive power exchange with the main grid, as evidenced by a lower cumulative reactive power demand (252.539 MVAR compared to 274.861 MVAR in the original). This reduction directly contributes to minimizing system losses and lowering operational costs.

Furthermore, the higher cumulative reactive power observed in terminals 1 and 2 under the modified methodology (147.217,74 MVAR versus 125.047,62 MVAR in the original) does not indicate inefficiency in the system as a whole. Instead, it reflects a strategic redistribution of reactive power demands within the system to achieve a more balanced and optimized interaction with the main grid.

In summary, while the reactive power activity at individual terminals may appear more pronounced in the modified methodology, the significant reduction in cumulative reactive

power exchanged with the main grid underscores the overarching goal of the modified approach: to optimize system-wide efficiency. This is achieved by reducing the overall reliance on and interaction with the main grid, thereby improving the system's economic and energy performance in its entirety.

In summary, the reactive power analysis provides two key conclusions:

- (a) For terminals 1 and 2, the modified methodology achieves greater overall system efficiency but results in higher reactive power variations and peaks. The original methodology, although more stable, appears less optimized for dynamic power allocation.
- (b) The overall improvement in system efficiency provided by the modified methodology compensates for the increased variability at specific terminals, ensuring a more cost-effective and balanced operation.

This progression, from renewable power generation to apparent power and finally to reactive power analysis, highlights the interconnected nature of these evaluations. It reinforces the advantages of the modified methodology in achieving a more efficient, dynamic, and adaptable system design, despite localized increases in reactive power demand.

The comparison of results between the original and modified methodologies reveals significant improvements in the modified approach, particularly in its ability to enhance renewable energy utilization and overall system efficiency.

Table 11: Comparison of Total Values with Percentage Difference

Metric	Original [kWh]	Modified [kWh]	Difference (%)
P_buy-P_sell MGrid	579,797.02	574,462.52	-0.92%
P_renew 1	22,346.27	25,022.81	+11.97%
P_renew 2	42,471.15	44,918.15	+5.76%
TOTAL Renewables	64,817.42	69,940.96	+7.91%
TOTAL (All Columns)	644,403.48	644,614.45	+0.03%

Starting with energy metrics, the modified methodology demonstrates a clear reduction in the reliance on the main grid, as evidenced by a slight decrease in the net energy exchanged with the grid (-0.92%). This reduction, while modest, highlights a more effective use of the available renewable resources, which is further supported by the observed increases in photovoltaic (P_{renew1}) and wind (P_{renew2}) energy generation. Photovoltaic generation sees an impressive increase of nearly 12%, while wind energy generation grows by over 5%. As a result, the total renewable energy contribution to the system increases by 7.91%, showcasing the modified methodology's ability to prioritize and maximize renewable energy production. Notably, these gains in renewable integration are achieved without disrupting the overall energy balance, which remains nearly unchanged (+0.03%).

Beyond energy generation, the financial and performance metrics in Table 12 further emphasize the benefits of the modified methodology. While the investment in renewable energy infrastructure (I_{ren}) increases by 7.9%, this higher upfront cost is offset by significant reductions in other areas. System losses decrease by 1.82%, reflecting a more efficient power flow and better energy management. The cost of the multiport converter (MPC)

Table 12: Comparison of Results: Modified vs Original Scenarios

Variable	Original	Modified	Difference (%)
I _{ren} (€)	90,993.69	98,186.35	+7.9%
Losses (kWh)	891.65	875.42	-1.82%
MPC Cost (€)	258,300.30	186,471.78	-27.8%
Objective Function (€)	1,364,395.20	1,261,816.33	-7.518%

sees a dramatic reduction of nearly 28%, highlighting the efficiency gains in the modified approach’s sizing and resource allocation. Overall, these improvements lead to a 7.518% reduction in the objective function value, a key measure of system performance that confirms the cost-effectiveness of the modified methodology.

In summary, while the modified methodology requires a slightly higher investment in renewable energy, this is compensated by its ability to integrate renewables more effectively, reduce dependency on the main grid, lower system losses, and achieve a more cost-effective design for the multiport converter. The result is a system that enhances energy efficiency and aligns with the goals of sustainability and economic optimization. These findings highlight the superiority of the modified methodology in achieving a well-balanced and optimized energy system.

5 Planification

In order to ensure the development of the project, the timeline and objectives were defined previously over different periods of time.

The project started in March 2024, with the first part of the project including the definition of the problem and analysis of the data, when it was developed the methodology for dimensionality reduction and clustering, until the validation of the method in September 2024. Then, the second part of the project focused on the definition of the new methodology for sizing the MPCs, which was developed and validated from September 2024 until January 2025, when the results were analyzed.

Figure 41: Project Workflow and Planning Overview

6 Economic assessment

This section detailed the budget needed to develop this project, considering the software, computer equipment, and human resources. The master's thesis consists of 42 ECTS and has a workload of approximately 30 hours/ECTS, amounting to approximately 1260 hours of total dedication. Based on the guidelines from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, the minimum hourly salary is set at 10 €/h [75], summing to 12,600.00 € as the total cost of the human resources, counting from the time of my internship in March until the final submission date.

According to the simulations, it was included the electricity cost of running a laptop with a minimum power of 15 W and a maximum of 90 W. Considering that the whole time the project was developed with the laptop, the total energy consumption averaged between the maximum and minimum power of the laptop (0.0525 kW) and the total hours of dedication, being a total energy consumption of 66.15 kWh and electricity cost of 0.1652 €/kWh [76], assuming a total cost for electricity of 10.92 €. The cost of the laptop was of 1200 € and it could be amortized in 7 years, leading to an annual amortization cost of 172 €. According to the durability of 1 year of duration of this project, the total amortization cost is of 172 €.

It has included the transportation cost from home to the university, considering the public transport, which implies the tariff per month of the T-jove being 42.7 €/month, considering 7 months of tariff, assuming a total of 298.9 €.

The cost of software and access to scientific literature has not been included, due to the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya was providing that service free for students, offering institutional licenses for essential software such as Python. This support from the university has significantly reduced the project's overall cost while ensuring access to state-of-art tools and publications.

Table 13: Project Budget Breakdown

Description	Units	Unit Cost (€)	Total Cost (€)
Human resources	1260 hours	10.00 €/hour	12,600.00
Electricity consumption	66.15 kWh	0.1652 €/kWh	10.92
Laptop amortization	1 year	172.00 €/year	172.00
Public transportation	7 months	42.70 €/month	298.90
Subtotal			13,081.82
IVA (21%)			2,747.18
Final Total			15,829.00

7 Environmental assesment

This section details the environmental assessment according to the CO₂ emissions primarily associated with the transport and electricity consumption required for the development of the project.

Considering the electricity mix, which expresses the CO₂ emissions associated with the electricity generation that is consumed, it becomes possible to estimate the environmental

impact. According to a publication by the CNMC [77] on April 25, 2024, the mix of the Spanish electricity network is 260 g CO₂eq/kWh.

Additionally, the public transportation usage, being the metro, contributed to the project's environmental footprint. Based on the location of my residence in Les Corts, being a distance of 2.6 km per trip. Counting two trips per day, five days a week, over six months (February to July), the total distance is 624 km. This calculation considers recurrent travel to and from the university during the development of the thesis. The CO₂ emissions from the metro could be calculated by the emission factor provided by Transport Metropolitans de Barcelona (TMB) [78], which is 23.7 g CO₂eq/km.

Using this emission factor, the CO₂ emissions resulting from the electricity consumed during the project's development can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ Emissions (kg)} = \frac{\text{Electricity Consumed (kWh)} \times \text{Electricity Mix (g CO}_2\text{eq/kWh)}}{1000} \quad (7)$$

Table 14: Total CO₂ emissions resulting from the development of this thesis.

Source	Quantity	Specific Emissions	Total Emissions [kg CO ₂ eq]
Electricity consumption	66.15 kWh	260 g CO ₂ eq/kWh	17.20
Metro (per commute)	2.6 km/trip	23.7 g CO ₂ /km	0.06
Metro (total commutes)	624 km	23.7 g CO ₂ /km	14.79
Total	—	—	31.99

Figure 42: Pie chart distribution of CO₂ emissions

The total amount of CO₂ emissions for the master thesis is 31.99 kg CO₂. The use of public transportation, particularly the metro, played a pivotal role in minimizing emissions compared to more carbon-intensive alternatives like private vehicles. Moreover, efficient energy use at home further reduces the overall environmental footprint.

While this work has a modest direct carbon footprint, its broader contributions aim to support the transition to sustainable energy systems. By advancing knowledge and methodologies that promote cleaner and more efficient energy distribution, this research aligns with global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and foster a sustainable future in the energy sector.

8 Social and gender equality assessment

The main objectives of this master thesis are aligned with most of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [79], particularly focused on energy efficiency, sustainability, and innovation. The most relevant SDGs addressed by this project include:

Directly Related SDGs

- **SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy)**: The integration and optimization of **MPCs** consist of the improvement of the efficiency and flexibility of renewable energy productions. According to the goal of reducing losses and supporting the better integration of renewable resources such as solar and wind energy, the project is contributing directly to making the energy systems more affordable due to the reorganization of the power flow distributions and contributing to this renewable energy making a system more sustainable.
- **SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure)**: according to the advanced **MPC** technologies analyzed on the project, it represents an innovation in power system optimization, focused on the ensemble-based optimization, it involves the improvement of the current grid infrastructures with an innovative solution, scalable and cost-effective in energy systems.
- **SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities)**: This methodology and technology can be implemented into the existing grid topologies within urban environments. It supports the efficient integration of renewable energy sources, ensuring operational reliability and energy availability for the urban population. Additionally, the flexibility and scalability of **MPCs** make them suitable for isolated regions such as low-density populated regions or mountainous regions with microgrids formed by renewable energy, typically isolated. The methodology provides an opportunity to enhance energy access to this location where the traditional grid infrastructure is normally limited or economically not feasible to expand.

Indirectly Related SDGs

- **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)**: The use of optimization techniques in electrical power flows ensures that resources are used efficiently, reducing the losses of the system and maintaining the balance between the consumption and production due to the interconnection and flexibility of the multiport converters. The **MPCs** supports the shift towards sustainable energy production and encourages responsible resource use, helping to minimize waste and overproduction,
- **SDG 13 (Climate Action)**: It promotes the transition to a low-carbon energy system by integrating renewable technologies and storage systems. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions and supporting the adoption of renewable energy contribute to mitigating the effects of global warming and climate change.
- **SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals)**: the research has been done in collaboration with different entities as **CIGRE**, which provided information on grid topologies and case studies. These partnerships ensure the analysis of the viability and integration in real-world scenarios.

The project not only has a direct impact on specific SDGs but also contributes indirectly to broader goals. While SDGs 7,9 and 11 are at the core of this research, the SDGs 12,13 and 17 are interconnected due to the nature of sustainable development.

Figure 43: Key SDGs Supported by This Research

This thesis reflects a commitment to inclusivity by employing non-discriminatory language and emphasizing equality to avoid biases related to gender, race, or cultural norms. It reflects a real commitment to guarantee equality, ensuring that the advancements and the solution proposed can benefit all sectors of society without exclusion or discrimination. Moreover, the master thesis emphasizes the importance of providing affordable and accessible clean energy technologies to different communities, which also could be often marginalized in the energy transition.

Conclusions

The proposed methodology comprehensively addresses the challenge of optimizing the sizing and operation of multi-port converters (MPCs) in electricity distribution networks, reducing investment costs and computational complexity. Through the combination of machine learning techniques (autoencoders) and clustering methods (K-means), representative days capture the key features and patterns of the datasets, reducing the cases of studies in order to analyze the most relevant scenarios for the optimization sizing process of the MPCs. This approach avoids the usual over-dimensioning - by simultaneously considering the interaction between the different terminals and energy resources - and significantly speeds up the optimization stage.

Initially, a sensitivity analysis was performed on a high-dimensional dataset encompassing wind, PV generation, and consumption profiles to evaluate the quality of clustering. However, the maximum Silhouette Score obtained was 0.25, indicating inadequate cluster compactness and preventing effective data visualization. Consequently, an autoencoder was introduced to reduce dimensionality to a three-dimensional latent space, enabling more robust clustering, improved visualization, and a higher Silhouette Score of 0.4164. K-means identified 13 representative days through this refined approach, further validated by an MSE of 0.012027. This reduction in dimensionality significantly lowers computational requirements without compromising model accuracy or result quality.

Subsequently, two scenarios were briefly considered: one with a lower share of renewables and another with higher renewable penetration. Although specific details from the lower-renewable scenario are not discussed here, the comparison showed that an increased share of renewables further enhances the benefits of the global MPC sizing methodology over the traditional terminal-by-terminal approach. These findings underscore both the scalability of the methodology and the pivotal role of higher renewable integration in achieving

more efficient MPC optimization.

A direct comparison of the original (terminal-by-terminal) versus the modified (global) methodology underscores the advantages of the latter. As shown in the performance tables, main-grid dependence decreases by 0.92%, and total renewable output increases by 7.91%. Concurrently, total MPC costs drop by 27.8%, and the objective function value is reduced by 7.518%. These results highlight a more balanced utilization of energy resources, reduced reliance on external supply, and greater incorporation of renewables, ultimately validating the technical and economic feasibility of the global sizing strategy.

The methodology was tested on a network of 33 IEEE standard buses, incorporating data from the iPLUG project and additional test scenarios. Optimizing MPCs in a single, interconnected framework—rather than treating each terminal separately—this approach prevents over dimensioning caused by localized peaks in demand or generation. Instead, terminals can share capacity and adjust power flows according to real-time needs, which increases overall flexibility. The demonstrated results provide a clear basis for future work to refine the selection of representative patterns, integrate new energy resources, and improve the optimization process. Ultimately, this method offers a practical and scalable way to modernize power distribution networks, ensuring both economic benefits and greater sustainability.

Future Work

Although dimensionality reduction and clustering methodologies have been used to select representative days, the computational time required is still considerably high. In addition, the large number of possible configurations in MPC systems allows multiple scenarios to be generated and analyzed.

Therefore, the following lines of work are proposed for the future:

- **Increasing the number of representative days:** With more computational power available, a larger number of representative days should be analyzed to improve the accuracy and optimization of the results.
- **Optimisation of MPC terminal locations:** Integration of a new methodology to optimize MPC terminal connections, taking into account technical and economic criteria.
- **Scalability and renewable energies:** To evaluate the scalability of the system with the integration of higher proportions of renewable energy generation, also including hybrid AC/DC configurations.

These lines of future work will contribute to improving the capacity of modern distribution systems and facilitate a higher penetration of renewable energies while ensuring operational efficiency and sustainability.

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Annex

Annex A: Clustering results

Representation of Input, Latent Space, and Reconstruction

The following examples present the transformation of input data into latent space representations and reconstructed outputs. These visualizations highlight the model's ability to compress and reconstruct the original input while preserving essential features.

Figure 44: Example 1 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output

Figure 45: Example 2 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output

Figure 46: Example 3 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output

Figure 47: Example 4 Input, Latent Representation, and Reconstructed Output

Representative Daily Profiles Across Clusters: PV, WIND, and Consumption

The following graphs illustrate the representative daily profiles of PV, WIND, and Consumption for selected clusters. These visualizations highlight the temporal behavior of each variable within the clusters, showcasing differences in their daily patterns and variability.

Figure 48: Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 0 and 1 over Time

Figure 49: Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 2 and 3 Over Time

Figure 50: Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 4 and 5 Over Time

Figure 51: Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 6 and 7 Over Time

Figure 52: Representative Daily Profiles for Clusters 8 and 9 Over Time

Figure 53: Representative Daily Profiles for Cluster 10 and 11 over Time

Figure 54: Representative Daily Profiles for Cluster 12 over Time

Boxplot of each Variable by Cluster

The following boxplots present the distribution of each variable (PV, WIND, and Consumption) across the identified clusters. These visualizations highlight how the variables differ within and between clusters, providing a detailed view of their variability.

Figure 55: Boxplot of PV Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis

Figure 56: Boxplot of WIND Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis

Figure 57: Boxplot of Consumption Values: Cluster-Specific Analysis

Annex B: Optimization Process MPC

Representation of Input, Latent Space, and Reconstruction

Figure 58: Voltage differences across the different methodologies

Figure 59: Line current differences across the different methodologies